

City of Gresham Natural Hazards Policy and Program Review

Photos courtesy of City of Gresham

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FINAL Report

Prepared for
City of Gresham
1333 NW Eastman Parkway
Gresham, OR 97030

Prepared by
The University of Oregon
Institute for Policy Research & Engagement
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About the Institute for Policy Research and Engagement

**School of Planning, Public
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The Institute for Policy Research & Engagement (IPRE) is a research center affiliated with the School of Planning, Public Policy, and Management at the University of Oregon. It is an interdisciplinary organization that assists Oregon communities by providing planning and technical assistance to help solve local issues and improve the quality of life for Oregon residents. The role of IPRE is to link the skills, expertise, and innovation of higher education with the transportation, economic development, and environmental needs of communities and regions in the State of Oregon, thereby providing service to Oregon and learning opportunities to the students involved.

About Community Planning Workshop

Community Planning Workshop (CPW) is an experiential program within the Department of Planning, Public Policy and Management at the University of Oregon. Students work in teams under the direction of faculty and Graduate Teaching Fellows to develop proposals, conduct research, analyze and evaluate alternatives, and make recommendations for possible solutions to planning problems in Oregon communities. The CPW model is unique in many respects but is transferable to any institution that desires to link pedagogy with community service.

About the Oregon Partnership for Disaster Resilience

The Oregon Partnership for Disaster Resilience (OPDR) is a coalition of public, private and professional organizations working collectively toward the mission of creating a disaster-resilient and sustainable state. Developed and coordinated by IPRE, the OPDR employs a service-learning model to increase community capacity and enhance disaster safety and resilience statewide.

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Executive Summary

Background

This project builds on ongoing local, state, and federal initiatives aimed at strengthening and enhancing local hazard identification, assessment, and risk reduction activities for the City of Gresham, Oregon. The primary objective is to conduct a gap analysis by reviewing and analyzing City-identified hazard policies, programs, and activities to develop recommendations for improvements that aim to increase resilience. Defining ‘resilience’ in the natural hazard framework is helpful in establishing a baseline for all of the City plans to work from. We found that the plans have varying definitions for resilience. In short, this report provides specific practices that can be applied and integrated into the City’s policy and program framework for hazard and risk reduction.

To gain a thorough understanding of current policies and programs, the IPRE Student Team (project team) engaged with a multi-disciplinary team from the city, referred to in this report as the Steering Committee. To inform the gap analysis, the Steering Committee directed the IPRE Student Team to review existing city, county, and state documents including:

- Oregon Resilience Plan
- DOGAMI Hazard Risk Report for the Lower Columbia-Sandy Watershed
- Multnomah County Natural Hazards Mitigation Plan
- City of Gresham Comprehensive Plan
- City of Gresham Development Code
- City of Gresham Capital Improvements Plan

Upon reviewing existing documents and engaging with the Steering Committee, the project team developed a set of recommendations for updates to Gresham’s plans, programs, and policies which include both regulatory and non-regulatory approaches. The next section provides more detail on these two approaches.

Strategies for Risk Mitigation: Regulatory and Non-Regulatory

Hazard programs and policies discussed in this report include regulatory (i.e., non-voluntary) and non-regulatory (i.e., voluntary) strategies. There are functional differences between these strategies for hazard risk mitigation. Analysis in this report focuses on identifying easily implementable, cost-effective methods for increasing resilience in the City of Gresham. A key objective of this report is to expand the the current hazard mitigation planning framework to include a holistic view of community resilience. Resilient cities acknowledge the compounding effects of climate change on the frequency and intensity of natural hazard risks. Ensuring that policies, plans, and programs address climate change impacts makes cities more adaptable, able to recover sooner, and address vulnerabilities in the City’s planning process.

Non-regulatory Strategies

Non-regulatory plans include voluntary action items and programs that the City can adopt to improve their overall natural hazard resilience. Put simply, non-regulatory programs are not required but are recommended for a municipality to enhance aspects of their community. The Gresham portion (Chapter 4) of the Multnomah County Natural Hazards Mitigation Plan (NHMP) uses the following Multidisciplinary

Center for Earthquake Engineering Research’s definition of **disaster resilience**: The ability of communities to “mitigate hazards, contain the effects of disasters when they occur, and carry out recovery activities in ways that minimize social disruption and mitigate the effects of future disasters.”¹ The non-regulatory documents are essential in providing voluntary action items and programs that the City can adopt to improve their overall natural hazard resilience.

Regulatory Strategies

The City’s regulatory policies and programs offer tools and enforceable action items that are in place to reduce natural hazard risk for the community. Regulatory policies and programs are required by local, state, and federal jurisdiction and aim at enhancing the community. Gresham provides a somewhat comprehensive set of natural hazard policies, that are currently being implemented, within its regulatory documents that we reviewed. As will be discussed in the report, these regulatory strategies include methods to enhance natural hazard mitigation but are less informative on resilience tools.

Findings and Recommendations

After reviewing City of Gresham, regional, and state regulatory and non-regulatory documents, we synthesized our findings and recommendations into three categories 1. Hazards and Resilience; 2. Catastrophic Hazards; and 3. Chronic Hazards. The following findings and recommendations offer a summary of the more detailed findings in Chapters 2 and 3 of the report. The recommendations detailed in Chapter 4 include implementation suggestions and examples from other communities and projects where relevant. These recommendations are provided to enhance and strengthen Gresham’s current natural hazard policy and program framework.

Source: [Campus Resilience Case Study](#)

Hazards and Resilience

The IPRE team analyzed the non-regulatory guidance documents to determine (1) how ‘resilience’ is defined and (2) how resilience and climate change are integrated. Across non-regulatory plans, the analysis found inconsistencies in definitions of ‘resilience’ and weak connections between resilience and climate change.

Key Findings

- Gresham does not use a consistent definition of resilience throughout its planning and policy documents. The NHMP includes the following Rockefeller Foundation definition for resilience: "Resilience is essentially the flip side of vulnerability. It is the ability to 'survive, adapt, and grow in the face of stress and shocks, and even transform when conditions require it.'" Resilient communities not only anticipate, absorb, adapt to, and recover from disruptions quickly, but they also use disruptions as a catalyst for growth.
- There are weak connections between resilience and climate change in some plans, but the connection is clear in other plans.
- The NHMP offers four (4) goals for disaster-resilient communities and integrates the effects of climate change into each hazard type. These include:

¹ Multidisciplinary Center for Earthquake Engineering Research, 2004.

- 1) strengthening capacity through hazard awareness, partnerships, and multiple funding and implementation options
 - 2) developing mitigation actions that consider all community systems
 - 3) increasing social equity, and
 - 4) planning for including mitigation activities during post-disaster recovery and reconstruction
- “Resilience” is not explicitly mentioned or defined in local documents.
 - “Natural hazards” are mostly discussed in relation to Oregon State Goal 7.
 - “Climate Change” is not mentioned pertaining to hazards in regulatory documents.

Recommendations²

- Adopt and include a common definition of resilience throughout Gresham’s planning and policy documents. We recommend the City start by reviewing the current definition referenced in the NHMP and then consider alternative definitions such as: Resilience is the ability to anticipate, absorb, adapt to, and recover from crises and other disruptive events.³
- Update Comprehensive plan, section 10.2000 Areas Subject to Natural Hazards to include the NHMP’s disaster resilience goals.
- Develop a multi-lingual Hazard Mitigation Outreach Toolkit to increase equity and serve vulnerable populations.
- Establish a Safety Committee and seek partnerships with the private sector in mitigation planning.
- Create an incentive package for natural hazard resilience efforts. These could include seismic retrofit of privately-owned structures, green infrastructure such as bioswales and eco-roofs, etc.
- As part of ongoing local climate action, hazard mitigation, and community resilience planning efforts, partner with Oregon Climate Change Research Institute (OCCRI) to learn more about climate change impacts specific to Gresham. Use the [Northwest Climate Toolbox Workbook](#) to involve community in climate planning.
- Complete and publish an inventory of emergency shelters available to house vulnerable populations during both catastrophic (i.e., earthquake) and chronic (i.e., severe winter storms, extreme heat, wildfire smoke) hazard events.
- Consider risks in unincorporated areas (including, but not limited to, Pleasant Valley and Springwater) so that potential impacts on vulnerable populations are identified and continuously reviewed. Ensure that internal controls (regulations, maps/inventory, etc.) adequately mitigate current and future risks in unincorporated areas.
- As part of the 2022 NHMP update, add an action item for Gresham to regularly monitor and audit hazard mitigation efforts in the City’s highest risk areas.
- Update all hazard maps in Gresham and unincorporated areas

Catastrophic Hazards

For the purposes of this report, we define catastrophic hazards as those which happen at low frequency, but high severity. With anticipation of the 9.0 magnitude Cascadia Subduction Zone (CSZ) earthquake, seismic activity is identified as a catastrophic hazard. Landslides are a secondary effect of earthquakes due to liquefaction. Liquefaction markedly reduces the soil’s stability and can create significant damage to the built environment. Soils with loose, wet sediments are particularly vulnerable, especially near rivers.

² Some of the recommendations related to the categorized findings are more general or relate to multiple hazards, so they are categorized more generally.

³ Adapted from the 2009 National Infrastructure Advisory Council definition.

The steep slopes in Gresham place surrounding communities at an increased risk for earthquake induced landslides as well.

Key Findings

- Earthquake is the primary catastrophic hazard identified in the plans reviewed.
- Gresham’s earthquake risk to critical infrastructure is low.
- Gresham lacks private sector involvement in seismic planning efforts.
- Powell Valley Elementary School and the communities of Springwater and Pleasant Valley are at greater risk for earthquake damage.
- The Comprehensive Plan specifically addresses the earthquake hazard and includes policy language directing the city to adopt regulations that protect the public from earthquake hazards.
- Policy language addressing neighborhood-specific risks, inventory of earthquake shelters, or incentive programs for private seismic retrofit was absent from the Comprehensive Plan.
- The Development Code mitigates earthquake-induced landslide risk through the Hillside Physical Constraint Overlay District.
- The Development Code’s sections for Pleasant Valley and Springwater do not address hazards.
- The CIP includes projects involving seismic retrofit of critical infrastructure.
- Earthquake induced liquefaction is a risk in north Gresham in low-lying areas near the Columbia river near Marine Drive. Liquefaction is not directly addressed in the city zoning or development code.

Recommendations

- Establish a Seismic Safety Committee and seek partnerships with the private sector in mitigation planning.
- Update all hazard maps in Gresham and unincorporated areas.
- Apply for an Oregon Seismic Rehabilitation Grant Program grant to retrofit the Powell Valley Elementary School.

Chronic Hazards

These include landslides, wildfire, severe weather, and flood. Localized flood events are common in Gresham, but are generally not severe. Additionally, the NHMP rates Gresham at low flood risk. Given this, our team chose to focus on landslides, severe weather and wildfire.

Findings

- The NHMP identifies landslide risk areas and references critical infrastructure at risk of landslide damage, but does not identify them specifically.
- While non-regulatory plans identify wildfire hazard as a low risk in Gresham; we found only limited consideration of the future impacts of climate change on the wildfire hazard.
- Severe storms are discussed as secondary hazards to the larger hazard events Gresham experiences.
- The Comprehensive Plan outlines a robust policy framework for mitigating landslides and severe storm-related damage, but not for wildfires.
- Gresham’s existing zoning and development codes regulate hillside development through the Hillside Physical Constraint Overlay District; Gresham is in the process of updating its Hillside Overlay Zone to better address and mitigate landslide risk.
- Gresham’s existing zoning and development codes regulate development in flood plains; Gresham recently updated its Floodplain Overlay Zone to better address and mitigate flood risk.

- The CIP contains one project related to landslide and erosion mitigation from severe storms, but nothing regarding wildfires.

Recommendations

- Inventory the 33 buildings identified by the NHMP as at risk for landslide damage. Note if they are in the Springwater and Pleasant Valley communities. Following FEMA model, recommend acquiring and demolishing or relocating these buildings.
- Consider post-flood and windstorm building evaluation (ATC 45, ATC 20).
- Review and update the Hillside Physical Constraint Development overlay zone if new hazard inventory information becomes available.

Chapter 1: Introduction

This project builds on ongoing local, state, and federal initiatives aimed at strengthening and enhancing local hazard identification, assessment, and risk reduction activities for the City of Gresham, Oregon. The primary objective is to review and analyze City-identified hazard policies, programs, and activities to develop improvement recommendations that increase resilience. In short, this report provides specific practices that can be applied and integrated into the City’s policy and program framework for hazard and risk reduction.

Background

Oregon communities face increasing natural hazard risk and vulnerability. Increased vulnerability elevates the importance of mitigating natural hazards and increasing disaster resilience through utilizing risk reduction strategies. Such efforts range from disaster preparation methods, coordination within and across sectors, and regeneration abilities for post-disaster recovery. According to the Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), “resilience’ depends on the whole community — individuals, families, and households; communities; nongovernmental organizations; private-sector entities; local governments; regional agencies; state governments; and the federal government. Inclusiveness and partnership across the whole community ensures the best use of available knowledge, resources and efforts.”⁴

Investment in hazard mitigation and risk reduction efforts can save money for local and state governments in the long-term, while protecting community assets and saving lives during and after a disaster. On average, for every \$1 spent on pre-disaster mitigation efforts, there is a savings of \$6 in post-disaster recovery efforts. For example, flood mitigation efforts have a \$7 post-disaster savings for every \$1 spent on pre-disaster mitigation efforts while earthquake mitigation efforts have a \$4 post-disaster savings for every \$1 spent on pre-disaster mitigation.⁵ This data signifies the financial benefit of natural hazard planning that is important to community resilience practices during and after a disaster event.

FEMA was created to provide emergency support for and response to natural hazard events in the United States. In 2009, FEMA created the Risk Mapping, Assessment, and Planning (Risk MAP) program to improve flood maps and provide hazard mitigation tools and strategies for communities to strengthen and enhance local ability to address risk.⁶ In Oregon, the Oregon Risk MAP program is an extension of federal Risk MAP program to create state-specific flood maps, tools, and strategies and to provide more localized natural hazard support. Through Oregon Risk MAP, a variety of local, state, and federal resources are available for hazard mapping, assessment, and planning efforts each year. These efforts are currently led by FEMA’s Region X with the Oregon Department of Geology and Mineral Industries (DOGAMI) and IPRE as Cooperating Technical Partners (CTP). IPRE has been a CTP since 2014.

⁴ Multnomah County Emergency Management. Multnomah County Multi-Jurisdictional NHMP. 2017.

⁵ FEMA. Natural Hazard Mitigation Saves Interim Report. 2018.

⁶FEMA. What is Risk MAP?. 2012.

Gresham’s Risk Mitigation Strategies

There are functional differences between strategies for risk mitigation. This section provides an overview of Gresham-specific non-regulatory (i.e., voluntary) and regulatory (i.e., non-voluntary) strategies reviewed and analyzed to develop findings and recommendations. The City of Gresham directed the IPRE Student Team to review the below outline plans for this report. Any related plans not reviewed were not included in our synthesis as per instruction by the City. This report is a gap analysis of select city, regional, and state documents, not all available City plans.

Table 1: Plans Reviewed⁷

Plan Title	Year	Jurisdiction
Oregon Resilience Plan	2013	Oregon
DOGAMI Natural Hazard Risk Report for the Lower Columbia-Sandy Watershed	2018	Multnomah and Washington Counties
Multnomah County Natural Hazards Mitigation Plan	2017	Multnomah County
City of Gresham Comprehensive Plan	2004	City of Gresham
City of Gresham Development Code	2019	City of Gresham
City of Gresham Capital Improvement Plan	2019	City of Gresham

Oregon Resilience Plan, 2013

The Oregon Resilience Plan (ORP) addresses seismic resiliency. In particular, the ORP establishes a decision-making framework for local agencies to determine resilience performance gaps and identify courses of action including but not limited to capital investments, incentives, and policy changes. This is relevant for the City of Gresham as the city is situated in a valley with multiple buttes around its edges. This topography places the city at an increased risk for earthquake-induced landslides. [DOGAMI’s HazVu](#) mapping feature shows Gresham’s risk is moderate relative to other parts of the region, with strong shaking expected.⁸ Notably, the City of Gresham’s water distribution system, which runs through these buttes, is at significant risk for breakage and leakage from seismic activities. The plan’s recommendations include specific action items that the City can implement to improve the water and wastewater system resiliency.⁹

⁷ The IPRE Student Team only reviewed specific plans and documents as directed by the Gresham Steering Committee. For additional information on why plans were included or omitted, please reach out to Tina Osterink.

⁸ See Chapter 2 for images and additional information on Gresham’s relative risk of earthquake-induced landslides.

⁹ Oregon Seismic Safety Policy Advisory Commission. The Oregon Resilience Plan. 2013.

DOGAMI Natural Hazard Risk Report for the Lower Columbia-Sandy Watershed (2018)

The DOGAMI Natural Hazard Risk Report for the Lower Columbia-Sandy Watershed (Risk Report) details results of DOGAMI's 2017 natural hazard risk assessment for the Lower Columbia-Sandy Watershed. The watershed area lies at the western edge of the Columbia River Gorge, inclusive of Multnomah County and thus Gresham. The report provides an up-to-date, detailed natural hazard risk assessment to improve the decision-making processes in disaster planning. Recommendations are categorized by natural hazard preparation, including awareness, planning, regulation, emergency response, mitigation funding opportunities, and as risk reduction activities.¹⁰ There are specific findings and recommendations for the City of Gresham.

Multnomah County Natural Hazards Mitigation Planning (2017)

The Disaster Mitigation Act of 2000 requires local governments to create a Natural Hazards Mitigation Plan (NHMP) in order to receive Hazard Mitigation Assistance (HMA) funding. HMA includes the Pre-Disaster Mitigation grant program, the Hazard Mitigation grant program, and the Flood Mitigation Assistance grant program.¹¹ Locally, NHMPs are reviewed by the Oregon Office of Emergency Management (OEM) and approved by FEMA. The City of Gresham is included in the Multnomah County Multi-Jurisdictional NHMP, which is updated every 5 years with the next anticipated update in 2022. The plan establishes county-wide hazard mitigation goals, objectives and actions to reduce recovery time and improve disaster preparedness.¹² The goal is to protect people, critical infrastructure, the environment, and private property from natural hazards. It serves as an evaluative tool to inform decisionmakers how to best utilize their resources. Evaluation criteria utilized include: (1) equity, (2) benefits, (3) costs, (4) risk, and (5) capacity.¹³

Gresham Comprehensive Plan (2004 Update)

Each city in Oregon is required by law to create a Comprehensive Plan. The plan must address and comply with 19 statewide planning goals, anticipate land use needs for the next 20 years, and be updated periodically as cities grow and change. The Gresham Comprehensive Plan was designed to meet such parameters and definitions required by the Oregon Revised Statutes. In particular, the Gresham Comprehensive Plan includes Volume 1: Findings; Volume 2: Policies and Implementation Strategies; Volume 3: Community Development Code; Volume 4: Transportation System Plan; and Volume 5: Capital Improvement Program.

Gresham Community Development Code

Volume 3 of the Comprehensive Plan, The Gresham Community Development Code, establishes and outlines standards and procedures for development, including but not limited to height, density, and functional use. The City is currently updating portions of the Development Code to clarify guidelines and standards for certain types of development.

¹⁰ DOGAMI. Natural Hazard Risk Report for the Lower Columbia-Sandy Watershed. 2018.

¹¹ Multnomah County Emergency Management. Multnomah County Multi-Jurisdictional NHMP. 2017.

¹² Ibid.

¹³ Multnomah County Emergency Management. Multnomah County Multi-Jurisdictional NHMP. Table 4.2-2. Mitigation Action Prioritization Criteria. 2017, pp.182.

Gresham Capital Improvement Plan (CIP)

The Gresham CIP is updated and adopted annually and reflects the city's planned investments in public infrastructure and utilities such as stormwater, transportation, water, wastewater, and parks over a five-year timeframe. It identifies funded and unfunded capital projects.

Project Purpose and Approach

The purpose of this project is to build on the City of Gresham's prior work with FEMA, DLCD, and DOGAMI. It is an opportunity to use a multi-objective approach to resiliency and risk reduction planning. The primary objective is to review and analyze City-identified hazard policies, programs, and activities to develop recommendations for improvement for consideration by the City. IPRE seeks to provide realistic, cost-effective, and feasible natural hazard mitigation policy and action options. For technical support and guidance for this project, IPRE and the City of Gresham formed a Steering Committee comprised of a multi-disciplinary team of Gresham staff.

Figure 1: Map of Gresham, OR

City of Gresham. Source: Google Earth

Figure 2: Earthquake Susceptibility Map

Color-coded earthquake hazard map, Gresham outlined in black. Source: State Library of Oregon

Project Approach

Our analysis focuses on identifying easily implementable, cost-effective methods for increasing resilience within the City of Gresham. Resilient cities acknowledge the compounding effects of climate change on the frequency and intensity of natural hazard risks, making cities more adaptable to change, able to recover sooner, and able to address vulnerabilities in planning processes. The key research elements include: (1) content analysis of the City's policy and program framework and (2) interviews with Steering Committee members. This approach is described below.

Content Analysis

The IPRE team conducted an analysis of local, regional, and statewide documents to develop recommendations (See Appendix B, Figure 10: Content Analysis Approach). We began with an initial presence/absence search of 15 key terms before narrowing the list to terms of greatest relevance to

hazard mitigation and resilience (i.e., ‘resilience’, ‘climate change’, ‘livability’, and ‘mitigation’) (See Appendix C). Specifically, the team reviewed the fact bases, goals, policies, and actions across the documents detailed in Table 1 and the Gresham Risk Mitigation Strategies section above. This search led to the identification of notable gaps in the plans. From there, we noted the frequency of the key terms and then assessed the relevance to hazard mitigation and resilience. The team used an ordinal scale to independently identify and assess the degree of detail, Each and then compared results in order to validate intercoder reliability.

Results from this analysis were organized by hazard type: (1) earthquakes, (2) landslides, (3) severe weather, and (4) wildfire. Findings were then compared against a 2013 FEMA report titled, “Mitigation Ideas: A Resource for Reducing Risk to Natural Hazard,” which is a comprehensive document that recommends hazard specific risk reduction actions and programs.¹⁴ This comparison allowed us to see areas of strength for Gresham, as well as areas where they could add or modify policy tools to align with FEMA’s recommendations. These findings were synthesized across plans in order to determine improvement recommendations.

Figure 3: Content Analysis Approach

Steering Committee Interviews

The IPRE Team conducted four interviews with selected members of the Steering Committee in February 2020. Interviewees were solicited based on their involvement with policy and code implementation. Each individual team member conducted one 30 to 45-minute phone interview with City staff from the

¹⁴ FEMA. Mitigation Ideas: A Resource for reducing Risk to Natural Hazards. 2013.

Departments of Environmental Services and Urban Design & Planning. The interviews followed a predeveloped interview guide (See Appendix C) that covered questions within three categories:

1. General Information including staff roles and baseline knowledge of resiliency;
2. Specific hazard policy needs based on the interviewees knowledge and area of expertise; and
3. Information about the City's current hazard policy and program framework.

Transcriptions of the interviews allowed the team to further synthesize information into key themes, which helped inform the team's analysis and assessment of the City's policy and program framework.

Organization of Report

The remainder of this report is separated into non-regulatory (Chapter 2) and regulatory (Chapter 3) findings. Chapter 4 includes an implementation framework. We provide additional supporting figures, tables, and supporting documents in the Appendices.

Chapter 2 provides a summary of non-regulatory policy and program recommendations from IPRE's analysis. It includes a review and synthesis of the NHMP, the Risk Report, and the ORP to provide background on how the IPRE team came to their recommendations.

Chapter 3 provides a summary of regulatory policy and program recommendations from IPRE's analysis. It includes a review and synthesis of the City of Gresham's Comprehensive Plan, Development Code, and the Capital Improvement Plan to provide background on how the IPRE Student Team came to their recommendations.

Chapter 4 provides implementation recommendations for the regulatory and non-regulatory policy and program updates. Building from Chapters 2 and 3, this chapter includes actionable items for the City to utilize when implementing recommendations through their policy and program framework.

Appendix A provides a community profile with additional background information on the City of Gresham.

Appendix B provides a detailed logic model which supports our content analysis process and the interview guide used during Steering Committee interviews.

Chapter 2: Non-regulatory Plan Assessment

This chapter presents key findings from analysis of the non-regulatory guidance documents reviewed for this report, namely the ORP, Risk Report, and NHMP.¹⁵ Key findings are organized by natural hazard area and type, beginning with general hazards and resilience followed by catastrophic hazards (e.g. earthquakes) and then chronic hazards (e.g. landslides, wildfire, and severe weather). Analysis focuses on identifying easily implementable, cost-effective methods for increasing resilience in the city of Gresham. The following findings inform recommendation and implementation tools discussed in Chapter 4.

Hazards and Resilience – Findings

The IPRE team analyzed the non-regulatory guidance documents to determine (1) how ‘resilience’ is defined and (2) how resilience and climate change are integrated. Across non-regulatory plans, the analysis found inconsistencies in definitions of ‘resilience’ and weak connections between resilience and climate change. Key findings are described as follows.

Key Finding: Gresham does not use a consistent definition of resilience throughout its planning and policy documents.

The ORP follows the Oregon Seismic Safety Policy Advisory Commission (OSSPAC) definition of resilience and focuses on resilience through the lens of community, critical infrastructure and economic growth, whereby stronger critical infrastructure strengthens communities and supports economic growth.¹⁶ The OSSPAC’s definition of resilience is as follows: “Oregon citizens will not only be protected from life-threatening physical harm, but...because of risk reduction measures and pre-disaster planning, communities will recover more quickly and with less continuing vulnerability following a Cascadia subduction earthquake and tsunami.”¹⁷ To ground its resilience definition, the ORP uses the “resilience triangle” wherein resilience is correlated to service, time and recovery.¹⁸

The Risk Report also discusses resilience in terms of risk reduction but does not include a definition of resilience. Rather, the report provides broad parameters for resilience by stating, “awareness and preparation not only reduce the initial impact from natural hazards it also reduces the amount of recovery time for a community to bounce back from a disaster – this ability is commonly referred to as ‘resilience.’”¹⁹ As such, the report suggests that improving response time can contribute to improved resilience, offering a recommendation to identify areas of vulnerability and raising awareness within these areas in the event of a disaster.²⁰ This resonates with the language in the ORP.

¹⁵ The IPRE Student Team only reviewed specific plans and documents as directed by the Gresham Steering Committee. For additional information on why plans were included or omitted, please reach out to Tina Osterink.

¹⁶ Oregon Seismic Safety Policy Advisory Commission. The Oregon Resilience Plan. 2013, pp 241.

¹⁷ Oregon Seismic Safety Policy Advisory Commission. The Oregon Resilience Plan. 2013, pp 161.

¹⁸ Oregon Seismic Safety Policy Advisory Commission. The Oregon Resilience Plan. 2013, pp 185.

¹⁹ DOGAMI. Natural Hazard Risk Report for the Lower Columbia-Sandy Watershed. 2018, pp 47.

²⁰ DOGAMI. Natural Hazard Risk Report for the Lower Columbia-Sandy Watershed. 2018, pp 48.

Figure 4: Resilience Triangle

The resilience triangle is used in the ORP and provides context for how resilience impacts recovery efforts after a natural disaster. Source: Oregon Seismic Safety Policy Advisory Commission. (2013). The Oregon Resilience Plan.

The NHMP discusses resilience in terms of disaster-resilient communities. Disaster-resilient communities are able to reduce hazard risks, contain the effects of disasters, and perform recovery actions that lessen future hazard risks.²¹ To define resilience, the NHMP refers to the Rockefeller Foundation's definition: "resilience is essentially the flip side of vulnerability. It is the ability to 'survive, adapt, and grow in the face of stress and shocks, and even transform when conditions require it' (The Rockefeller Foundation, no date)."²² To achieve a disaster-resilient community, the NHMP provides guidance through four actions: (1) capacity building (e.g. increasing awareness, creating partnerships, leveraging funding and implementation), (2) a multi-objective approach to action development (i.e., economic, health, housing), (3) prioritization of cost-effective and socially equitable actions, and (4) post-disaster recovery planning.

Resilience refers to a community's ability to *anticipate, absorb, adapt to, and recover from disruptions*. **Resilient communities** not only respond to and bounce back from disruptions quickly, but they also use *disruptions as a catalyst for growth*.

While the Rockefeller Foundation's definition is key for the NHMP, the following definition more clearly describes resilience. Resilience refers to a community's ability to anticipate, absorb, adapt to, and recover from disruptions. Resilient communities not only respond to and bounce back from disruptions quickly, but they also use disruptions as a catalyst for growth. For more discussion on this, refer to Chapter 3 of this report.

²¹ Multnomah County Emergency Management. Multnomah County Multi-Jurisdictional NHMP. 2017. pp. 15.

²² Multnomah County Emergency Management. Multnomah County Multi-Jurisdictional NHMP. 2017. pp. 11.

In addition to the inconsistencies outlined above in how non-regulatory documents define resilience, key stakeholder interviews revealed a lack of shared understanding at the staff level about how resilience is defined and envisioned. One participant described resilience in terms of seismic building codes, environmental standards (e.g. energy, natural resources—tree code provisions), and transportation (emergency routes, maintenance and alternative transportation modes). Another described it in terms of social equity and community resilience. Another emphasized climate resilience and suggested having a chapter dedicated to this in the Comprehensive Plan. Overall, most participants described resilience topically, rather than as an overarching vision. While it is clear that members of the Gresham Steering Committee generally understand what resilience is and how it can apply to the city, the lack of an “enterprise wide” understanding of resilience across city divisions and departments hinders the effectiveness of resilience planning. More detailed information on how resilience is referred to is presented in Chapter 3 of this report.

In summary, resilience is inconsistently defined based on a lack of shared understanding, both in non-regulatory documents and amongst City staff. The ORP focuses on infrastructure resilience to strengthen communities. The Risk Report describes resilience loosely based on identification of vulnerabilities to reduce risk and improve recovery time. The NHMP discusses resilience in terms of hazard risk reduction, containment, and recovery that decreases communities’ risk level. In our steering committee interviews, City staff tended to discuss resilience topically. While each of the nonregulatory documents and city departments are working towards resilience based on their roles, the lack of a uniform vision impedes planning for resilience. These findings indicate a need to develop an overarching vision statement that the City can use to guide future hazard mitigation planning documents at the local and county level, including the Comprehensive Plan, the NHMP and Gresham’s Climate Action Plan.

Key Finding: There are weak connections between resilience and climate change in some plans, but the connection is clear in other plans.

The ORP briefly describes the relationship between climate change, natural hazard risk vulnerability, and community resilience.²³ The only reference to climate change is in the *Looking Ahead* section, wherein the ORP alludes to future research needed. The next iteration may include more detail on the impacts of climate change as more research and information has become available in the last seven (7) years.

In the NHMP, climate change is addressed within each natural hazard risk assessment. Each section describes the compounding effects of climate change on the frequency and intensity of natural hazards’ risks and how they impact one other. However, no information is available at the local level. The most reliable information on climate change is only available at the state level according to the Oregon NHMP (2015).²⁴

In summary, climate change is well-linked in some plans, but not others. The ORP briefly connects natural hazard risk to community resilience and climate change but does not focus on this. The NHMP discusses the impacts of climate change on each natural hazard type. These findings indicate a gap in policy language in linking climate change and resilience. Given Gresham’s lack of a definition for resilience and its current work towards developing a Climate Action Plan as well as upcoming work on the 2022 NHMP, the City has an opportunity to ensure a consistent framework for addressing resilience and climate change integration across its plans.

²³ Ibid.

²⁴ Multnomah County Emergency Management. Multnomah County Multi-Jurisdictional NHMP. 2017.

Hazards & Resilience Key Takeaways:

Nonregulatory

- ✓ The NHMP extensively links climate change and resilience while the ORP does not.
- ✗ No information about climate change is available at the local level in the ORP or the NHMP.
- ✓ Definitions and approach of resilience are inconsistent between City of Gresham staff as well as between the ORP, the Risk Report, and the NHMP.
- ✗ City of Gresham staff lack consistent language that mirrors the NHMP's four actions to increase resilience.

Catastrophic Hazards – Findings

For the purposes of this report, we define catastrophic hazards as those which happen at low frequency, but high severity. A 9.0 magnitude Cascadia Subduction Zone (CSZ) earthquake is the primary catastrophic hazard of concern in Gresham. Notably, Gresham may also experience a number of secondary hazards commonly associated with earthquake shaking. These include earthquake induced landslides (e.g. on Gresham's buttes), soil liquefaction (e.g. in low-lying areas with loose, wet sediments near the Columbia River), and structural fires (e.g. associated with broken gas lines). Notably, volcanic eruption of Mt. Hood presents some potential for severe impacts in Gresham. However, mapping completed by DOGAMI indicates only moderate impacts associated with lahar activity that are limited to the Sandy River corridor and Columbia River confluence.

Key Finding: Earthquake is the primary Catastrophic hazard identified in the plans reviewed.

The ORP, Risk Report, and NHMP all view seismic activity as a catastrophic hazard. The ORP focuses mainly on earthquake resilience, so the entire report provides strong background information and implementation ideas for statewide seismic risk reduction and recovery. Additionally, it links landslides to the post-CSZ earthquake. The Risk Report includes action items to mitigate earthquake risk and recovery while the NHMP identifies recovery times for various infrastructure based on current building and community information. The NHMP categorizes Gresham at a high level of risk for earthquake-induced landslides due to its dense population and built environment. Both private and public infrastructure is at risk from the CSZ. These non-regulatory reports supplement each other by including information about different aspects of seismic hazard mitigation and resilience.

Findings from the ORP, Risk Report and NHMP generally fall into the following categories: (1) focus on infrastructure resilience in seismic hazard policy, (2) emphasis on coordinating with the private sector and the public for seismic risk reduction planning through incentive packages for seismic retrofit and development regulations, and (3) identification of at-risk buildings and communities. These are discussed in further detail below.

Key Finding: Gresham’s earthquake risk to critical infrastructure is low.

Based on our review, Gresham’s critical infrastructure is resilient overall. Gresham is incorporating resilience considerations into its critical infrastructure planning. For example, Gresham’s plans include provisions for assessing and improving seismic resistance of bridge infrastructure, supporting the ORP’s recommendation to inventory and fund critical transportation routes.²⁵ Similarly, Gresham has both Water and Wastewater System Seismic Resilience Plans that supports the ORP’s recommendation to conduct seismic risk assessment and retrofitting of water and wastewater facilities. These connections to the City’s regulatory hazard framework show that Gresham is already incorporating seismic hazard risk reduction policy. These regulatory programs and policies will be discussed further in Chapter 3.

In summary, Gresham has strong planning around infrastructure resilience. These efforts revolve around bolstering the City’s water, wastewater, and transportation systems.

Key Finding: Gresham lacks private sector involvement in seismic planning efforts.

The ORP, Risk Report and NHMP recommend coordinating with the private sector for seismic risk reduction planning. Engaging with the private sector to increase resilience and post-disaster actions increases community resilience and builds capacity by involving a broader group of stakeholders. Currently, the City has a Green Business Program which certifies businesses for environmental conservation efforts but does not include the private sector in seismic planning in its programs or as a strategy in its Comprehensive Plan. Additionally, the Steering Committee reported a need for private sector representation on the NHMP committee. With a planned update for the 2022 NHMP, the City and Multnomah County have an opportunity to act on this. The Steering Committee also expressed interest in connecting with the Planning Commission and Chamber of Commerce in this.

The ORP recommends developing an incentive package for seismic resilience. This includes creating a seismic rating system for future building construction that goes above the requirements of the building code.²⁶ The Risk Report recommends raising awareness of need for seismic retrofit among home and business owners.²⁷ The Steering Committee noted that crafting an incentive package would receive weak support due to financial costs. The City will need to find a way to work with local contractors and possibly provide discounts, such as the utility rebate program they are developing.

The Risk Report also recommends regulating development in highly liquefiable soil areas to reduce risk.²⁸ Gresham’s Development Code regulates development in landslide risk areas through the Hillside Physical Constraint Overlay District. This is discussed in more detail in Chapter 3.

In summary, Gresham lacks private sector involvement in seismic resilience planning, but has an opportunity to engage with them by expanding their Green Business Program and by including them in the 2022 NHMP update. Creating an incentive package for seismic retrofitting will face financial and political barriers unless discounts are provided to local contractors. Gresham’s Development Code regulates development in landslide risk areas through the Hillside Physical Constraint Overlay District.

²⁵ City of Gresham Capital Improvement Plan. 2019, pp. 144

²⁶ Oregon Seismic Safety Policy Advisory Commission. The Oregon Resilience Plan. 2013, pp xxi.

²⁷ DOGAMI. Natural Hazard Risk Report for the Lower Columbia-Sandy Watershed. 2018, pp 61.

²⁸ Ibid.

Key Finding: Powell Valley Elementary School and the communities of Springwater and Pleasant Valley are at greater risk for earthquake damage.

The Risk Report and NHMP specify at-risk public and private buildings in Gresham. The Risk Report includes a community profile for Gresham, which is intended to “encourage ideas for natural hazard risk reduction” by identifying level of risk for each hazard, and by including a list of critical infrastructure that may be impacted by a hazard event.²⁹ It does not discuss, however, the criteria used to classify a building as high risk in the event of a seismic event or otherwise. The Risk Report identifies Powell Valley Elementary School as the only public facility at risk for moderate to severe damage.³⁰ The ORP specifically mentions [Oregon’s Seismic Rehabilitation Grants Program](#) as a potential funding source for critical public facilities, including K-12 schools, community colleges, and emergency response facilities.

Based on feedback from the Steering Committee, the Gresham-Barlow School Districts owns the facility and therefore infrastructure retrofits would be funded and implemented by the District. The 2022 NHMP update could note the need for upgrades to Powell Valley Elementary School since it is within Multnomah County.

The NHMP identifies the communities of Springwater and Pleasant Valley at particular risk for earthquake-induced landslides due to their proximity to heavily sloped terrain. Gresham addresses landslide risks using zoning and development code standards. Based on our review of the Springwater and Pleasant Valley District Plans, it was not clear the extent to which existing development standards or restrictions apply in these areas. Notably, there may be other planning documents and codes that provide regulations for these areas that our review did not include. The Steering Committee noted that the city is currently undergoing code updates for natural resource areas and the Natural Resources department is monitoring these areas annually due to state and federal regulation. As these areas develop, we recommend the City of Gresham ensure that earthquake risks are covered through existing or revised zoning and development code standards.

Figure 5: Liquefiable Soils Map in South Gresham

Map depicting earthquake liquefiable soils around Pleasant Valley. Source: DOGAMI HazVu.

²⁹ DOGAMI. Natural Hazard Risk Report for the Lower Columbia-Sandy Watershed. 2018, pp 53.

³⁰ DOGAMI. Natural Hazard Risk Report for the Lower Columbia-Sandy Watershed. 2018, pp 61.

In addition to the areas discussed above, DOGAMI’s HazVu mapping shows areas of earthquake liquefiable soils.³¹ NE Marine Drive along the Columbia River is at high risk. Sandy Boulevard is at low risk. The area around Pleasant Valley/Powellhurst-Gilbert is at high risk. Kelley Creek along the southern edge of Gresham has areas from low to high risk of liquefiable soils. Butler Creek, to the east of Jenne Butte, has areas of mostly low risk of liquefaction to high risk along the creek.

In summary, the findings related to retrofitting the Powell Valley Elementary School is important for Gresham to support, but this effort is to be led by the Gresham-Barlow School District. The Springwater and Pleasant Valley communities are part of the natural resource areas being monitored annually. However, it is important to confirm that these vulnerable populations have the necessary land-use regulations in place to reduce catastrophic earthquake risks.

Figure 6: Liquefiable Soils Map in North Gresham

Map depicting earthquake liquefiable soils along the Columbia River. Source: DOGAMI HazVu Map.

Catastrophic Hazards Key Takeaways: Nonregulatory

- ✓ Risk Report cited Powell Valley Elementary School as the only public facility at risk for moderate to severe earthquake damage.
- ✓ NHMP points out the communities of Springwater & Pleasant Valley in Gresham at particular risk for earthquake-induced landslides.
- ✓ ORP connects landslides to post-CSZ earthquake.

Chronic Hazards – Findings

For the purposes of this report, we define chronic hazards as hazards that occur on a semi-regular basis. These include landslides, wildfire, severe weather, and flood. Localized flood events are common in Gresham, but are generally not severe. Additionally, the NHMP rates Gresham at low flood risk. Given this, our team chose to focus on landslides, severe weather and wildfire. The ORP, Risk Report, and NHMP address all three hazards. The primary themes of recommendations are: (1) create maps and inventory areas and critical buildings that are subject to these hazards, (2) regulate development in areas subject to

³¹ DOGAMI. (2020). Retrieved from <https://gis.dogami.oregon.gov/maps/hazvu/>.

hazards, (3) provide private sector incentives to build/retrofit structures to hazard-resilient standards, and (4) invest in hazard-resilient critical infrastructure.

Climate change considerations are taken into consideration in some instances. In the future, Gresham’s policy and program framework may need to be adapted to account for increasing uncertainty caused by climate change effects on natural hazard mitigation planning. The City is currently working on a Climate Action Plan that may help inform the 2022 Multnomah County NHMP updates to provides greater clarity on the impacts of climate change on the various chronic hazards discussed in this report. The Risk Report and the NHMP provide the best guidance for shifts in language, while the ORP focuses on catastrophic natural hazard planning related to the CSZ earthquake. The following sections describe specificities for each chronic hazard, beginning with landslides, then moving to wildfires and severe weather.

Landslides

The Risk Report states that the region is susceptible to landslides, while the NHMP classifies Gresham at a moderate risk level for landslides following OEM criteria.³² Developed areas are located within landslide risk areas in Gresham. This leads to increased damages and losses to people and property. Changes in climate are expected to increase occurrences of severe weather, such as extreme rain events and flooding, which will induce landslides.³³ The ORP does not address the chronic nature of landslides as it focuses on this hazard as a secondary event to earthquakes.

Key Finding: The NHMP identifies landslide risk areas and references critical infrastructure at risk of landslide damage but does not identify them specifically.

The FEMA Risk Report identifies 40 buildings in Gresham at moderate risk and 1,044 buildings at high risk of landslide susceptibility. However, the report does not identify where these are specifically located.³⁴ Section 6.6.3 highlights four (4) actions for landslide risk reduction: (1) create landslide inventory and susceptibility maps, (2) control stormwater in landslide prone areas, (3) monitor for ground movement in high susceptibility areas, and (4) implement grading codes in high susceptibility areas.³⁵ To support this, the NHMP notes

Figure 7: Landslide Suseptability Map

Map depicting likelihood of landslide activity in the greater Gresham area. Source: DOGAMI HazVu Map.

³² The OEM ranks level of hazard risk by: (1) number of historical occurrences requiring a response; (2) percentage of population and property likely to be affected; (3) highest possible percentage of population or property impacted in worst-case scenario; and (4) likelihood of an event happening within a certain time period.

³³ Multnomah County Emergency Management. Multnomah County Multi-Jurisdictional NHMP. 2017.

³⁴ DOGAMI. Natural Hazard Risk Report for the Lower Columbia-Sandy Watershed. 2018, pp 66.

³⁵ DOGAMI. Natural Hazard Risk Report for the Lower Columbia-Sandy Watershed. 2018, pp 50.

that Springwater and Pleasant Valley, south-central Gresham and areas near the city's buttes, including Gresham Butte and Hogan Butte are at greater risk for landslides because of the heavily sloped terrain.³⁶ Policies and regulations are already in place for buttes and other parts of Gresham. See Chapter 3 for more information.

The NHMP mentions thirty-three (33) buildings in Gresham are at risk of landslide damage.³⁷ It does not, however, identify which buildings they are specifically, or their general location. The NHMP top mitigation action No. 32 recommends considering 2017 DOGAMI lidar-based landslide data to identify at-risk development and infrastructure. This data can be incorporated into comprehensive plans and development codes. This data can direct prioritization of mitigation projects.³⁸ This can also help identify the 33 at-risk buildings if the City does not have a list of them already. When discussed with the Steering Committee, they mentioned they would do additional research to identify the critical infrastructure.

In summary, while the non-regulatory reports mention the need for identifying critical infrastructure that is at risk of landslide damage, the documents require more specificity on which buildings are most susceptible. Because this inventory of critical infrastructure was mentioned in the regional non-regulatory documents, they can be updated with more specific information. The City's non-regulatory documents can provide updated landslide maps to identify landslide risk areas to continue updating the inventory of critical infrastructure in Gresham.

Wildfires

The ORP, Risk Report, and NHMP all mention wildfire hazard briefly, but all see this hazard as low priority compared with other natural hazards in the region. The ORP is a statewide resilience plan, but it does not need to include wildfire resilience recommendations or actions as that can be highlighted in local and regional short-term risk reports instead. According to the Risk Report, wildfires are seen as high probability, but low risk when compared with other hazards in the region.³⁹ The Risk Report provides some potential recommendations Gresham could implement and the NHMP includes an action item to address wildfires. While this data is brief, the regulatory documents discussed in Chapter 3 do not include any language directly related to wildfire resilience and mitigation. We identify key findings in the non-regulatory documents and relevant actionable items taken from each non-regulatory plan.

Key Finding: While non-regulatory plans identify wildfire hazard as a low risk in Gresham; we found only limited consideration of the future impacts of climate change on the wildfire hazard.

The ORP focuses mainly on seismic resilience and broad natural hazard resilience in the long-term. There is no mention of wildfire hazard mitigation or resilience actions or recommendations and the IPRE Student Team believes that wildfire is not within the scope of the ORP because of its focus on long-term, catastrophic natural hazard risk. Any mention of "fire" in the ORP is related to Fire and Rescue efforts, and so does not apply to the scope of this project. In comparing probability of different hazard types, the ORP states that wildfires are high probability, but does not detail the risk level associated with it. Section 6.6.4 of the Risk Report's Hazard Risk Reduction Actions outlines proposed actions for wildfire risk

³⁶ Multnomah County Emergency Management. Multnomah County Multi-Jurisdictional NHMP. 2017.

³⁷ Multnomah County Emergency Management. Multnomah County Multi-Jurisdictional NHMP. 2017.

³⁸ Multnomah County Emergency Management. Multnomah County Multi-Jurisdictional NHMP. 2017.

³⁹ DOGAMI. Natural Hazard Risk Report for the Lower Columbia-Sandy Watershed. 2018.

reduction and preparedness. The report recommends the following actions:

1. “Maintain building buffer areas from forestland, especially in the fire-prone wildland-user interface.”
2. “Reduce fuel loads in buffer areas that can act as firebreaks.”
3. “Evaluate post-wildfire geologic hazards including flood, debris flows, and landslides.”⁴⁰

Action Item No. 1 could be implemented as part of regulatory policy for Gresham. Action item 3 is helpful for general hazard mitigation in Gresham. More detail on the importance of this action would be beneficial in understanding how crucial it is for Gresham to implement. Based on OEM criteria, the NHMP categorizes Gresham at a low level of risk for wildfires. This is due to “low fuel loads and a break in potential fuel sources.”⁴¹

According to this, the fuel loads in buffer areas mentioned in action item 2 are not a problem currently, but this should be considered in the future in the case that the City expands into other wildfire risk areas. Wildfires and droughts are expected to increase with changes in climate causing hotter, drier summers; a decline in average summer precipitation; and decreases in mountain snowpack from warmer winters.

Generally speaking, South-Central Gresham (including portions of Springwater and Pleasant Valley) is at a higher risk of wildfire due to lower urban density and increased vegetation. While the NHMP has less detail on wildfire hazard, the City can look to its regulatory documents to provide policy and programs related to wildfire resilience and mitigation. The City of Gresham regulates new construction through development permits as specified in the City of Gresham’s Development Code. This will be discussed further in Chapter 3.⁴² The risk reduction action items outlined in the Risk Report can help to enhance and strengthen the City’s wildfire policy and actions.

Severe Weather

According to the Risk Report, severe weather is not considered a significant hazard by itself. Severe weather is an issue when it causes landslides and floods from heavy rain or when it causes wildfire spread from strong wind increases. Severe weather increases the damage and likelihood of other hazards. This contrasts with the NHMP, which places Gresham at a high-risk level for severe weather based on OEM criteria.

This includes heavy rain, windstorms, snow, ice, thunderstorms, hail, lightning, tornado, drought, and heatwave. Climate change models forecast hotter and drier summers and more extreme rain events. It is difficult to predict how exactly this will affect Gresham, but the frequency and severity of severe winter weather events is expected to increase over time. The ORP does not provide background on severe weather since it is focused on seismic resilience.

Key Finding: Severe storms are discussed as secondary hazards to the larger hazard events Gresham experiences.

The Risk Report does not address severe storm hazards specifically but references it as a cause of other hazard events such as landslides and floods. Similarly, the NHMP lacks Gresham-specific severe weather

⁴⁰ DOGAMI. Natural Hazard Risk Report for the Lower Columbia-Sandy Watershed. 2018, pp 50.

⁴¹ Multnomah County Emergency Management. Multnomah County Multi-Jurisdictional NHMP. 2017.

⁴² Multnomah County Emergency Management. Multnomah County Multi-Jurisdictional NHMP. 2017.

information. The ORP discusses that design-level windstorms can have a strong impact on homes and critical buildings. It suggests having certified building inspectors available for post-disaster inspections. The Applied Technology Council (ATC) provides post-flood and windstorm building evaluation (ATC-45). Through Steering Committee feedback, we discovered that many City employees recently completed critical infrastructure inspection training and are up to date on this.

The NHMP also noted that transportation systems are more frequently impacted by severe weather and are at a higher risk of damage than buildings. This is an interesting finding as most other hazard language in these plans discusses the impact on critical buildings. Considering the impact on roads and transportation systems this is important to consider especially as severe storm events are expected to increase. There is minimal data availability and research regarding changes in winter weather specific to the Pacific Northwest. Additionally, NHMP top mitigation action No. 48 recommends collaboration with Climate Action Plan Committee and City of Portland to lower effects of the urban heat island. This is particularly important in areas with vulnerable populations.

Chronic Hazards Key Takeaways:

Nonregulatory

- ✓ Overall, Gresham is at relatively low risk to most chronic hazards
- ✗ 33 buildings at risk of landslide damage in Gresham.
- ✗ Severe storm events expected worsen as climate changes.

Summary of Findings

We reviewed three (3) non-regulatory planning documents, the ORP, the Risk Report and the NHMP. We grouped our findings into themes of (1) Hazards and Resilience, (2) Catastrophic, and (3) Chronic. Our key findings for each theme include:

Hazards and Resilience

- Gresham does not use a consistent definition of resilience throughout its planning and policy documents. The NHMP includes the following Rockefeller Foundation definition for resilience: "Resilience is essentially the flip side of vulnerability. It is the ability to 'survive, adapt, and grow in the face of stress and shocks, and even transform when conditions require it.'" Resilient communities not only anticipate, absorb, adapt to, and recover from disruptions quickly, but they also use disruptions as a catalyst for growth.
- There are weak connections between resilience and climate change in some plans, but the connection is clear in other plans.
- The NHMP offers four (4) goals for disaster-resilient communities and integrates the effects of climate change into each hazard type. These include:
 - 1) strengthening capacity through hazard awareness, partnerships, and multiple funding and implementation options
 - 2) developing mitigation actions that consider all community systems
 - 3) increasing social equity, and

- 4) planning for including mitigation activities during post-disaster recovery and reconstruction

Catastrophic

- Earthquake is the primary catastrophic hazard identified in the plans reviewed.
- Gresham’s earthquake risk to critical infrastructure is low.
- Gresham lacks private sector involvement in seismic planning efforts.
- Powell Valley Elementary School and the communities of Springwater and Pleasant Valley are at greater risk for earthquake damage.

Chronic

- NHMP identifies landslide risk areas and references critical infrastructure at risk of landslide damage, but does not identify them specifically. The city’s existing zoning and development codes address hillside development and landslide risk.
- The non-regulatory plans identify wildfire hazards as low risk, but should consider the future impacts of climate change.
- Severe storms are discussed as secondary hazards to the larger hazard events Gresham experiences.

Conclusion

Chapter 3 discusses the regulatory findings that correlate to these non-regulatory findings. Chapter 4 will provide policy and action option recommendations based on findings from Chapter 2 and 3 as well as offer examples of how other communities implemented similar policies and actions. An implementation framework for the proposed recommendations will be outlined to provide a concise summary of proposed implementation techniques. The implementation section will illustrate how the IPRE Team views these recommendations being incorporated into the City of Gresham’s current framework.

Chapter 3: Policy and Code Implementation Frameworks

This chapter presents key findings from analysis of the regulatory guidance documents reviewed for this report: City of Gresham Comprehensive Plan Volume 2 (Policies), Volume 3 (Gresham Development Code), and Volume 5 (Gresham Capital Improvement Plan (CIP)).⁴³ Key findings are organized by natural hazard area and type, beginning with general hazards and resilience followed by catastrophic hazards (e.g. earthquakes) and then chronic hazards (e.g. landslides, wildfire, and severe weather). Analysis focuses on identifying regulatory gaps within the documents and suggests changes in order to increase resilience in the city of Gresham. The following findings inform recommendation and implementation tools discussed in Chapter 4.

Hazards and Resilience – Findings

Resilience refers to a community’s ability to anticipate, absorb, adapt to, and recover from disruptions. Resilient communities not only respond to and bounce back from disruptions quickly, but they also use the possibility of disruptions as a catalyst for growth. In order to do that, however, Gresham’s Comprehensive Plan and implementing ordinances need to support resilience principles. In general, Gresham’s Comprehensive Plan does not specifically present policies that support resilience. A key word search of the documents found that the language is less related to hazard reliance and more toward health and safety topics. Specific examples include ‘health’ (found 165 times), versus ‘recovery’ (found five times) or ‘resilience’ (found zero times). However, the framework for adding more sections related to Gresham’s efforts surrounding hazard mitigation is in place and could be implemented in said documents.

Key Finding: ‘Resilience’ is not explicitly mentioned or defined.

The term “resilience” is not mentioned or defined explicitly in the Comprehensive Plan. Hazards, mitigation, preservation, and sustainability are discussed in multiple contexts, some of which relate to resilience from natural hazards and disasters.

Key Finding: ‘Natural Hazards’ are mostly discussed in relation to Goal 7.

Natural hazards are discussed most frequently in Section 10.200 “Areas Subject to Natural Hazards,” relating to Statewide Planning Goal 7, which is to “protect people and property from natural hazards.” It references Goal 7’s definition of natural hazards, which are “floods (coastal and riverine), landslides, earthquakes and related hazards, tsunamis, coastal erosion and wildfires.”⁴⁴ Natural hazard areas are also described in 10.705 and 10.806 of the Comprehensive Plan in relation to Natural Resources.

⁴³ The IPRE Student Team only reviewed specific plans and documents as directed by the Gresham Steering Committee. For additional information on why plans were included or omitted, please reach out to Tina Osterink.

⁴⁴ City of Gresham. Comprehensive Plan – Volume 2. 2018, p.33

Key Finding: 'Climate Change' is not mentioned pertaining to hazards.

Climate change is only mentioned twice, in the context of energy sources and linking transportation, air quality, and land use. Climate change and its relationship to natural hazards or mitigation is not discussed in the Comprehensive Plan.

Hazards & Resilience Key Takeaways:

Regulatory

- ✓ Climate change is mentioned twice in the Comprehensive Plan: (1) energy sources and (2) linking transportation, air quality, and land use.
- ✓ The Comprehensive Plan mentions Statewide Planning Goal 7 and has sections dedicated to earthquake, landslides, and floods.
- ✗ No discussion of public engagement or private sector involvement in hazard mitigation planning.

Catastrophic Hazards – Findings

The Comprehensive Plan directly and thoroughly addresses seismic activity and earthquake hazards. Specifically, *Section 10.212 – Earthquake Hazards* outlines policies and actions aimed at mitigating the risks associated with proximity to and within the Cascadia Subduction Zone.⁴⁵ Similarly, the Development Code's *Hillside Physical Constraint Overlay District* appears to consolidate much of the Comprehensive Plan's seismic-related goals and policies into one regulatory measure. Additionally, the CIP contains a seismic retrofit project of critical infrastructure. IPRE could not confirm whether or not specific non-regulatory actions have been addressed within the regulatory documents. Specifically, nothing was found addressing the communities with higher risk, incentive programs for seismic retrofit, or an inventory of earthquake shelters.

Key Finding: The Comprehensive Plan specifically addresses the earthquake hazard and includes policy language directing the city to adopt regulations that protect the public from earthquake hazards.

Section 10.212 – Earthquake Hazards discusses the hazards associated with earthquakes (e.g. ground shaking, steep slopes, liquefaction), Gresham's susceptibility from being within the Cascadia Subduction Zone, and the City's approach to mitigation. The section includes five (5) policies for coordination with state and federal agencies, regulating development, and directing public facility investment to account for seismic risk. The section also specifies four (4) actions aimed at assessing and communicating seismic hazards and associated risk to the city and residents.⁴⁶ Building codes ensure all new construction meets IBC and IRC standards for resistance to ground shaking, and damage associated with earthquake-induced landslides.

⁴⁵ City of Gresham. Comprehensive Plan – Volume 2. 2018, p.46

⁴⁶ City of Gresham. Comprehensive Plan – Volume 2. 2018, p.51

Key Finding: Policy language addressing neighborhood-specific risks, inventory of earthquake shelters, or incentive programs for private seismic retrofit was absent from the Comprehensive Plan.

The non-regulatory documents reviewed frequently mention the elevated hazard risk that is present in the Springwater and Pleasant Valley communities, as well as other areas in close proximity to buttes and steep slopes. Despite this, the Comprehensive Plan does not discuss these localized elevated risks. Additionally, no language related to earthquakes, seismic activity, landslides, or liquefaction was found in *Appendix 5 - Public Facilities*, *Appendix 42 -Pleasant Valley District Plan*, or *Appendix 44 - Springwater Community Plan*. Even more, nothing was found regarding an inventory of earthquake shelters or private sector or creating incentive packages for businesses and homeowners to build or retrofit structures to better seismic standards, as recommended by the Oregon Resilience Plan.

Key Finding: The Development Code mitigates earthquake-induced landslide risk through the Hillside Physical Constraint Overlay District.

Section 5.0200, Article 5, Overlay District – Hillside Physical Constraint Overlay District (HPCD) ensures that development within the district comply with regulations that prevent erosion and landslides: “The purpose of the HPCD is to ensure that development in or adjacent to hillside areas occurs in such a manner as to, A. Minimize the potential for earth movement and resultant hazards to life and property...”⁴⁷ Construction on parcels with gradients in excess of 15% and 35% is regulated to minimize this risk according to threat posed by the site. The City of Gresham utilizes up-to-date mapping data from DOGAMI to track at risk areas on an ongoing basis.

Key Finding: The Development Code’s sections for Pleasant Valley and Springwater do not address hazards.

Sections 4.1400 - Pleasant Valley Plan District and *4.1500 - Springwater Plan District* mentions natural hazards only to say that these ordinances do not apply to work that is related or in response to natural hazards. “Emergencies,” as defined in these sections, refer to many natural hazards including but not limited to earthquakes. No language related to earthquakes, seismic activity, landslides, or liquefaction was found in any of the other sections reviewed.

Key Finding: The CIP includes projects involving seismic retrofit of critical infrastructure.

The Capital Improvement Plan lists a series of completed and ongoing projects related to seismic upgrades and retrofits. The Wastewater Chapter mentions that “key projects include...pending FEMA grant, seismic upgrades to a sewer line crossing over Johnson Creek.” The Wastewater System Seismic Resilience Plan states that the “project will provide a new seismic study for the wastewater system, including collections system, wastewater treatment plant and the lift stations.” The Water chapter states that “the program includes...proactive assessments of critical mains and safeguards for vital facilities such as seismic upgrades.” Finally, the Bridge Inspection, Monitoring, Maintenance section of the Transportation Chapter states that “plans for 2019 include updating the bridge report to include more detailed and robust seismic analysis of our bridges. The updated report will serve as a bridge masterplan.”⁴⁸

⁴⁷ City of Gresham Development Code, [5.02]-1

⁴⁸ City of Gresham Capital Improvement Plan, p.15

No language related to earthquakes, seismic activity, landslides, or liquefaction was found in the following chapters of the Capital Improvement Plan: Footpaths and Bikeways; Parks, Trails, and Open Space; General Development; Stormwater; and Urban Renewal.

Catastrophic Hazards Key Takeaways:

Regulatory

- ✓ Hillside Physical Constraint District overlay regulates development in areas prone to slope instability.
- ✓ CIP includes seismic retrofit projects.
- ✗ Retrofit of Powell Valley Elementary School.
- ✗ Emergency shelter inventory.
- ✗ Earthquake risks or mitigation policies for areas with elevated liquefaction risk.

Chronic Hazards - Findings

The Chronic Hazards covered in this section include landslides, severe storms, and wildfires. IPRE found that, in regards to the hazards associated with landslides and severe storms, the City of Gresham's regulatory documents addressed them in accordance with best practices. Wildfires, on the other hand, were mostly absent from the regulatory documents reviewed.

Landslide risk is mitigated through hazard-specific language in the comprehensive plan and development code. The risks to properties within the city are well addressed, though there may be a lack of documentation pertaining to Springwater and Pleasant Valley neighborhoods. The Comprehensive Plan does not address severe storm hazards directly, but several sections address the effects of severe rain and winter storm events, as well as how to mitigate them with regulations on development and site-specific landscape features. The development code contains several measures to encourage good drainage and curb erosion due to development. The Capital Improvement Plan contains one single plan aimed towards flood storage and wetland mitigation.

Given Gresham's urban/suburban context, wildfires are not emphasized in the City's regulatory documents. The state and county assess the wildfire risk to be "low" compared to other regional hazards. Even so, some lower-density areas with higher percentages of vegetation and tree canopy in Gresham could be at increased susceptibility to smaller urban conflagrations. This includes areas around Gresham, Hogan, and Gabbert Buttes which add slope and aspect consideration that potentially elevate their risk.⁴⁹

Key Finding: The Comprehensive Plan outlines a robust policy framework for mitigating landslides and severe storm-related damage, but not for wildfires.

Section 10.211 – Steep Slopes & Landslides of the Comprehensive Plan outlines an extensive policy framework to address the landslide hazard. For example, the plan specifically addresses landslides and

⁴⁹ See Figure 8: Gresham Wildfire Risk and Multnomah County Wildfire Protection Plan, City of Gresham Fire & Emergency Services - [Community at Risk](#).

unstable soils with eight (8) policy goals, including the creations of an inventory of hazard areas and buildings/infrastructure at risk, designating sloped areas as public open space, and raising public awareness about landslide hazards.⁵⁰ These policies are codified in Development Code sections 9.0505 – *Guarantees for Grading and Drainage*, 9.0514 – *Erosion Prevention and Sediment Control Measures During Construction*, and 9.0515 – *Establishing Protective Vegetative Cover Upon Completion of Final Grading*.

The Comprehensive Plan mentions additional regulations, contained in the Hillside Physical Constraint Overlay District (Development Code Section 5.0200), that reduce landslide damage risk. There are limitations on terraforming activities (cutting, grading, vegetation removal), runoff standards, and process triggers for geotechnical reporting on slopes with a 15% or larger grade.⁵¹ On slopes more than 35%, there are much greater development limitations.⁵²

While the Comprehensive Plan does not specifically address hazards related to severe winter weather and storms, it does include several sections refer to hazards associated with rainstorms and other severe weather events. It discusses vegetation and wetlands’ function to mitigate flooding and erosion from storms, flood risks associated with heavy winter storms and intense rain events in developed areas, and recommends landscape features for site-specific stormwater treatment and flooding risk from storms, particularly in Pleasant Valley and the Johnson Creek and Kelley Creek Watersheds. Nothing was found in regard to post-severe storm building inspection.⁵³

The Gresham’s southern border sits on a Wildland-Urban Interface (WUI), a zone between wildland and human development. Urban areas near or within WUI’s have a greater exposure to wildfire risk. Gresham does not address Wildfire within its Comprehensive Plan, Development Code, or Capital Improvement Plan. State and County documents recognize Wildfire as a risk to Gresham, however this is not reflected in Gresham’s regulatory documents.

Figure 8: Gresham Wildfire Risk

Risk of wildfire in the greater Gresham area.
Source: [City of Gresham](#)

⁵⁰ City of Gresham. Comprehensive Plan – Volume 2. 2018, pp 43-44

⁵¹ City of Gresham. Comprehensive Plan – Volume 2. 2018, pp 43-44

⁵² City of Gresham. Comprehensive Plan – Volume 2. 2018, pp 43

⁵³ Oregon Seismic Safety Policy Advisory Commission. The Oregon Resilience Plan. 2013, pp xiii

Key Findings: The city’s existing zoning and development codes regulate hillside development through the Hillside Physical Constraint Overlay District; Gresham is in the process of updating it’s Hillside Overlay Zone to better address and mitigate landslide risk.

The city’s existing zoning and development codes regulate development in flood plains; Gresham is in the process of updating its Floodplain Overlay Zone to better address and mitigate flood risk.

The Development Code contains multiple sections intended to address landslide issues in several places. As previously stated, *Section 5.0200 Hillside Physical Constraint Overlay District* (HPCD) mapping, tracking, and protecting hillsides in order to mitigate slope failure. The code defines what the city is required to do pertaining to slopes in *Section 5.0202* and addresses development standards in *Section 5.0220*. According to *Section 9.0500 Grading and Drainage and Stormwater Management Requirements*, when a proposal involves potential erosion or runoff problems, the Project Manager may require a geotechnical report for HPCD before development approval is given. *Section 9.1000 Tree Regulations* relates to landslide and severe storm hazards in that trees help promote soil stability, minimize surface water, run-off.

The Development Code applies restrictions to development in zones with flood hazards through the Flood Plain Overlay District. *Section 5.0120 Standards for Development* contains numerous provisions for minimizing flood damage, relating to anchoring, construction materials and methods, utilities, subdivision, and more.⁵⁴ Supplemental sections in chapter 9 specify requirements for grading, drainage, and tree removal to control erosion and stormwater flows.

Appendix 5.000 outlines standards and processes for the provision of stormwater facilities to meet development needs. The *Stormwater Management Manual* has sections for erosion prevention and sediment control, and appendices relating to facility sizing methods, planting, and design standards. The *Stormwater Management Plan* provides Low-Impact Development standards for Pleasant Valley and Springwater. *Public Works Standards* instructs contractors to suspend operations when weather creates conditions unfit for surface work. The Development Code does not specifically address wildfires.

Key Finding: The CIP contains one ongoing project related to mitigating landslide and erosion from severe storms, but nothing regarding wildfires.

Project *906101: Stream and Slope Stabilization* is currently the only landslide-related project in the Stormwater section. It seeks to mitigate slope failures along Johnson, Kelly, and Fairview Creeks. However, this project only pertains to slope stabilization along creeks, and no other projects address other slope stabilization needs in other areas of Gresham.

No language related to severe storms was found in the CIP: Overview; Wastewater; Water; Transportation; Footpaths and Bikeways; Parks, Trails, and Open Space; General Development; and Urban Renewal. The CIP also does not list any projects related to mitigating wildfire risk.

⁵⁴ City of Gresham Development Code, [5.01]-3-4

Chronic Hazards Key Takeaways:

Regulatory

- ✓ Potential flooding and erosion from severe storms well addressed in code.
- ✗ Greater landslide and wildfire risk in District Plans.
- ✗ 33 at-risk buildings in the Comprehensive Plan.
- ✗ Severe storm hazards impacted by climate change in the Comprehensive Plan.
- ✗ Post-severe storm building inspection.
- ✗ Substantive language addressing wildfire-related hazards or policies.

Summary of Findings

We reviewed three (3) regulatory planning documents, the City of Gresham Comprehensive Plan – Volume 2 (Policies), Volume 3 (Development Code), and Volume 5 (CIP). Our key findings for each theme include:

Hazards and Resilience

- ‘Resilience’ is not explicitly mentioned or defined.
- ‘Natural Hazards’ are mostly discussed in relation to Goal 7.
- ‘Climate Change’ is not mentioned pertaining to hazards.

Catastrophic Hazards

- The Comprehensive Plan specifically addresses the earthquake hazard and includes policy language directing the city to adopt regulations that protect the public from earthquake hazards.
- Policy language addressing neighborhood-specific risks, inventory of earthquake shelters, or incentive programs for private seismic retrofit was absent from the Comprehensive Plan.
- The Development Code mitigates earthquake-induced landslide risk through the Hillside Physical Constraint Overlay District.
- The Development Code’s sections for Pleasant Valley and Springwater do not address hazards.
- The CIP includes projects involving seismic retrofit of critical infrastructure.
- Earthquake induced liquefaction is a risk in north Gresham in low-lying areas near the Columbia river near Marine Drive. Liquefaction is not directly addressed in the city zoning or development code.

Chronic Hazards

- The Comprehensive Plan outlines a robust policy framework for mitigating landslides and severe storm-related damage, but not for wildfires.
- Gresham’s existing zoning and development codes regulate hillside development through the Hillside Physical Constraint Overlay District; Gresham is in the process of updating it’s Hillside Overlay Zone to better address and mitigate landslide risk.

- Gresham’s existing zoning and development codes regulate development in flood plains; Gresham is in the process of updating its Floodplain Overlay Zone to better address and mitigate flood risk.
- The CIP contains one project related to landslide and erosion mitigation from severe storms, but nothing regarding wildfires.
- The Development Code’s sections for Pleasant Valley and Springwater do not address hazards.

Conclusion

Chapter 4 comprises the IPRE team’s recommendations based upon the discoveries outlined in Chapters 2 and 3. The recommendations will address the gaps found within Gresham’s regulatory documents, as well as suggestions relating to easily implementable and cost effective non-regulatory actions.

Final Key Takeaways of Regulatory and Nonregulatory Strategies

- ✓ Sufficient controls for severe weather, landslide, and earthquake hazards.
- ✓ Seismic hazard policy focuses on infrastructure resilience.
- ✗ Lack of direct integration between climate change and resilience.
- ✗ Lack of uniformity of resilience across plans.
- ✗ Landslide, wildfire, and earthquake hazards addressed in Pleasant Valley and Springwater communities.
- ✗ Public/private sector engagement and involvement in hazard mitigation planning.
- ✗ Wildfire risk reduction policies and programs.

Chapter 4: Recommendations & Implementation

This chapter discusses recommendations that the IPRE team derived from the findings described in chapters 2 and 3, along with steps for implementation. This chapter begins with a description of proposed recommendations and notes based on discussions with the Steering Committee. Proposed recommendations are linked to relevant findings and include examples. Mitigation actions and regulations which were not included in our workshop with the City of Gresham steering committee are summarized in the section about “other considerations.” The chapter ends with a brief summary of the intended timeline and effects of the policy options, along with a conclusion of the project and its findings.

Figure 9: Relationship between Natural Hazards and Community Assets

Source: FEMA (2013). *Local Mitigation Planning Handbook*.

Recommendation	Hazards Addressed	Implementation / Process of Adoption	Timeline
<p>Consider defining resilience using definition found in Chapter 3 of this report: Resilience refers to a community’s ability to anticipate, absorb, adapt to, and recover from disruptions. Update Comprehensive plan, section 10.2000 Areas Subject to Natural Hazards to include the NHMP’s disaster resilience goals. These include: (1) strengthening capacity through hazard awareness, partnerships, and multiple funding and implementation options, 2) developing mitigation actions that consider all community systems, 3) increasing social equity, and 4) planning for including mitigation activities during post-disaster recovery and reconstruction.</p>	<p>General hazards</p>	<p>Initiate amendment to Comprehensive Plan. Type 4 approval process[?] (Josh's notes p.5)</p>	<p>1 - 3 years</p>
<p>Develop a multi-lingual Hazard Mitigation Outreach Toolkit.</p>	<p>General hazards</p>	<p>Collaborate with the Communications department and an external consultant if necessary, to create a pamphlet in multiple languages. Refer to Multnomah County's multi-language earthquake preparedness online resources as a guide.</p>	<p>6 months - 1 year</p>
<p>Establish a Safety Committee and seek partnerships with the private sector in mitigation planning.</p>	<p>General hazards</p>	<p>Expand Gresham's Green Business Program to include resilience efforts. Establish requirements for certification that shows sufficient hazard mitigation has been completed.</p>	<p>1 - 3 years</p>

<p>Create an incentive package for natural hazard resilience efforts. This includes seismic retrofit of privately-owned structures and green infrastructure.</p>	<p>General hazards</p>	<p>There are a few different ways that this can be completed. Partnering with private contracting firms that can offer the incentive is a way that reduces cost burden for the city. This City could establish their own incentive program that would require funding from the City.</p>	<p>Ongoing, start in the next 1 - 2 years</p>
<p>Partner with Oregon Climate Change Research Institute (OCCRI) to learn more about climate change impacts specific to Gresham. Use the Northwest Climate Toolbox Workbook to involve community in climate change planning.</p>	<p>General hazards</p>	<p>Josh Bruce to introduce Gresham to OCCRI contact. See example (include link here?) for an idea of framework and what to expect through a partnership like this.</p>	<p>1 - 2 years</p>
<p>Complete and publish an inventory of emergency shelters available to house vulnerable populations during both catastrophic (e.g. earthquake) and chronic (e.g. severe winter storms, drought, heatwave) hazard events.</p>	<p>General hazards</p>	<p>Inventory designated emergency shelter sites, compile and publish materials with mapped locations.</p>	<p>1 - 3 years</p>
<p>Develop and implement an enforcement priority plan that addresses at-high risk, newly developing areas (e.g. Pleasant Valley and Springwater) so that potential impacts on these vulnerable communities can be identified and continuously reviewed. Ensure that internal controls (regulations, maps/inventory, etc.) adequately mitigate elevated risk in these areas. As part of the 2022 NHMP updates, add an action item for Gresham to regularly monitor and audit hazard mitigation efforts in the city's highest risk areas.</p>	<p>General hazards</p>	<p>For code amendments, Planning Commission provides recommendation that is voted on by City Council, with opportunity for public to provide comment. Internal processes can be achieved through administrative action.</p>	<p>1 - 3 years</p>

Update all hazard maps in Gresham and unincorporated areas.	General hazards	Utilize established city review and update structure. Consider incorporation of and consistency with existing DOGAMI data.	Ongoing
Apply for an Oregon Seismic Rehabilitation Grant Program grant to retrofit the Powell Valley Elementary School.	Earthquake	Powell Valley is the responsibility of the School District; the City will communicate need for retrofit grant and connect District to possible grant programs.	1 - 3 years
Inventory the 33 buildings identified by the NHMP as at risk for landslide damage. Note if they are in the Springwater and Pleasant Valley communities. Following FEMA model, recommend acquiring and demolishing or relocating these buildings.	Earthquake, landslide	Follow up with Multnomah County and NHMP, identify the 33 buildings mentioned, and compare list to existing records/maps of vulnerable structures. Adjust existing records as necessary.	6 months - 1 year
Consider post-flood, windstorm, and seismic building evaluation (ATC 45, ATC 20).	Earthquakes, severe storms, floods	Some Gresham employees recently went through ATC training, so they are up to date on this process, but ensuring that individuals refresh their training annually will be important for long-term success.	Ongoing
Conduct regular updates to the Hillside Physical Constraint Development overlay zone.	Earthquakes, landslides	Utilize established city review and update structure. Consider incorporation of and consistency with existing DOGAMI data.	Ongoing
Implement a Wildland-Urban Interface Code	Wildfire	For code amendments, Planning Commission provides recommendation that is voted on by City Council, with opportunity for public to provide comment. Internal processes can be achieved through administrative action.	1 - 3 years

Proposed Recommendations

The IPRE Team received feedback from the Steering Committee on the above recommendations. We intend to modify the proposed recommendations based on additional feedback from the City of Gresham during their review of the report draft.

1. **Adopt and include a common definition of resilience throughout Gresham’s planning and policy documents. We recommend the City start by reviewing the current definition referenced in the NHMP and then consider alternative definitions such as: Resilience is the ability to anticipate, absorb, adapt to, and recover from crises and other disruptive events.**⁵⁵
2. **Update Comprehensive plan, section 10.2000 Areas Subject to Natural Hazards to include the NHMP’s disaster resilience goals.** These include: (1) strengthening capacity through hazard awareness, partnerships, and multiple funding and implementation options, 2) developing mitigation actions that consider all community systems, 3) increasing social equity, and 4) planning for including mitigation activities during post-disaster recovery and reconstruction. The Comprehensive Plan does not mention resilience nor contain resilience-related goals. The City can follow examples of a resilience framework from the ORP, Risk Report and NHMP. The NHMP represents the best example of this shift in narrative. It provides specific goals and objectives that the City can model.
 - a. Notes on Implementation: Funding for this recommendation will be challenging in the near term. Comprehensive Plan updates are time consuming. To reduce administrative and economic burden, the City could align its comprehensive plan update process with upcoming updates to 2022 NHMP and Gresham's current work on a Climate Action Plan.
 - b. Additional Resources: The City is interested in seeing examples of best practice models from other cities. The San Francisco Bay Area has a [Resilience Program](#) which was the result of a project in collaboration with FEMA and the EPA.
3. **Develop a multi-lingual Hazard Mitigation Outreach Toolkit to increase equity and serve vulnerable populations.** Gresham stated an interest in better communication with diverse communities. Gresham has a very diverse population⁵⁶. A multi-lingual hazard mitigation outreach toolkit provides hazard education and support for these communities. We did not find mention of this in the documents to-date.
 - a. Notes on Implementation: This can be a very detailed toolkit or a simple pamphlet that was discussed during the Steering Committee meeting. A pamphlet would take less time and resources to put together but would provide diverse communities with the information they need to be prepared in the event of a disaster. If the City chooses to create a more detailed toolkit, the City can collaborate with the Regional Disaster Preparedness Organization and 2022 NHMP update. Additionally, the City may consider applying for a Resilience Grant with the EPA. To better coordinate with the local community, the City can partner with a community liaison program to do outreach.
 - b. Additional Resources: [Multnomah County Emergency Preparedness Program](#)
4. **Establish a Safety Committee and seek partnerships with the private sector in mitigation planning.** This is a recommendation from the FEMA Mitigation Ideas Report. Promoting community resilience and livability through private sector partnerships helps with post-disaster

⁵⁵ Adapted from the 2009 National Infrastructure Advisory Council definition.

⁵⁶ See Appendix A for full community profile.

recovery. The ORP and Risk Report have relevant recommendations. The City has the Green Business Program but should expand to other categories.

- a. Notes on Implementation: The City can create a short-term ad hoc task force within Gresham's Planning Commission. Additionally, the City can connect with the Chamber of Commerce to build capacity among private sector in seismic planning. Funds for this recommendation could come from tip fees on solid waste collection, rather than the general fund.
 - b. Additional Resources: See [FEMA Mitigation Ideas Report](#) for additional information.
- 5. Create an incentive package for natural hazard resilience efforts. These could include seismic retrofit of privately-owned structures, green infrastructure such as bioswales and eco-roofs, etc..** The ORP and Risk Report recommend creating incentive packages to promote natural hazard resilience, but the City's regulatory documents do not mention any.
- a. Notes on Implementation: This is difficult to implement due to higher costs that affect the City and local contractors. Incentive programs can be done on a smaller scale such as the utility's "Treebate" program Tina discussed at the Steering Committee meeting.
 - b. Additional Resources: No additional resources at this time.
- 6. As part of ongoing local climate action, hazard mitigation, and community resilience planning efforts, partner with Oregon Climate Change Research Institute (OCCRI) to learn more about climate change impacts specific to Gresham. Use the Northwest Climate Toolbox Workbook to involve community in climate planning.** NHMP Action Item 9 recommends collaborating with state, regional, and academic organizations to coordinate projects related to risk analysis and reduction, specific to climate change. The [Northwest Climate Toolbox Workbook](#) is a product of OCCRI. The workbook was created for the residents of Spokane, WA to involve the community in climate change planning through the [Spokane Community Adaptation Project](#) . In addition to this workbook, OCCRI has an online resource tool to show the effects of climate change visually.
- a. Notes on Implementation: This can supplement or be done in tandem with the City's Climate Action Plan.
- 7. Complete and publish an inventory of emergency shelters available to house vulnerable populations during both catastrophic (e.g. earthquake) and chronic (e.g. severe winter storms, drought, heatwave) hazard events.** The ORP recommends an inventory of emergency shelters, especially for earthquakes. FEMA also mentioned heating centers for severe winter storm events involving mass power outages. Sheltering is a county responsibility, but the city government can connect people to services, even if it does not provide them.
- a. Notes on Implementation: Gresham's online emergency preparedness plan does not show an inventory of county-run shelters nor does it link to the Multnomah County emergency plan which offers more detail.
 - b. Additional Resources: No additional resources provided at this time.
- 8. Consider risks in unincorporated areas (including, but not limited to, Pleasant Valley and Springwater) so that potential impacts on vulnerable populations are identified and continuously reviewed. Ensure that internal controls (regulations, maps/inventory, etc.) adequately mitigate current and future risks in unincorporated areas.** Multiple documents recommended regulating development in hazard areas, and the state/county documents call out Pleasant Valley and Springwater as having particular risk for multiple hazards. There is currently a lack of provisions for these unincorporated areas.

- a. Notes on Implementation: City is currently completing code updates for natural resource areas (Environment Overlay Project). The project addresses development in floodplain and hillside areas. Gresham’s Natural Resources Program monitors at-risk areas, such as Springwater Woods, annually due to a push from state and federal monitoring regulations.⁵⁷
 - b. Additional Resources: No additional resources necessary at this time.
- 9. As part of the 2022 NHMP updates, add an action item for Gresham to regularly monitor and audit hazard mitigation efforts in the city’s highest risk areas.** Limited ongoing monitoring and measurement of hazard mitigation efforts exists.
- a. Notes on Implementation: City is currently completing code updates for natural resource areas (Environment Overlay Project). The project addresses development in floodplain and hillside areas. Gresham’s Natural Resources Program monitors at-risk areas, such as Springwater Woods, annually due to a push from state and federal monitoring regulations. There has been discussion around adding action items to the NHMP that include regularly monitoring and auditing hazard mitigation efforts, so we included that here to highlight its importance.
 - b. Additional Resources: No additional resources necessary at this time.
- 10. Update all hazard maps in Gresham and unincorporated areas.** City, county and state documents recommended keeping hazard maps up to date. The most recent landslides data map from DOGAMI is from 2017.
- a. Notes on Implementation: The City is planning to update its codes at the end of 2020. Consider linking with Emergency Operations Plan.
 - b. Additional Resources: No additional resources required at this time.
- 11. Apply for an Oregon Seismic Rehabilitation Grant Program grant to retrofit the Powell Valley Elementary School.** The Risk Report identified Powell Valley Elementary School as the only critical infrastructure at moderate to high risk of damage during a CSZ earthquake event.
- a. Notes on Implementation: Powell Valley is the responsibility of the School District. The City will need to communicate with the District of the need for a retrofit grant and connect them to possible grant programs.
 - b. Additional Resources: [Seismic Rehabilitation Grant Program](#)
- 12. Inventory the 33 buildings identified by the NHMP as at risk for landslide damage. Note if they are in the Springwater and Pleasant Valley communities. Following FEMA model, recommend acquiring and demolishing or relocating these buildings.** NHMP references 33 buildings but does not provide specific details on them, and we were unable to find mention of them in any of the other documents reviewed.
- a. Notes on Implementation: The Steering Committee is identifying these buildings, but more clarity and verification is needed.
 - b. Additional Resources: Robin Pederson began identifying these buildings after the meeting on March 11, 2020. Discuss with her to learn more information.

⁵⁷ Natural Resources Program, *City of Gresham*. <https://greshamoregon.gov/Natural-Resources-Program/>

13. **Consider post-flood, windstorm, and seismic building evaluation (ATC 45, ATC 20).** The ORP suggests having ATC certified building inspectors for post-disaster inspection of critical infrastructure.
 - a. Notes on Implementation: ATC-45 is post flood and ATC-20 is post-seismic. City of Gresham has current Building Inspectors who have been through ATC-45/20 training. The ATC provides in-person training seminars for building officials, building inspectors, engineers and others involved in post-disaster safety building inspections.
 - b. Additional resources: Use the [ATC-45 Field Manual: Safety Evaluation of Buildings after Windstorms and Floods as a guide](#). The ATC provides in-person [training seminars for building officials, building inspectors, engineers and others involved in post-disaster safety building inspections](#).
12. **Review and update the Hillside Physical Constraint Development overlay zone if new hazard inventory information becomes available.** Multiple documents referenced need for regularly updated maps.
 - a. Notes on Implementation: The City is currently in the process of updating its floodplain and hillside hazard maps.
 - b. Additional Resources: No additional resources.

Other Considerations

We created additional recommendations to consider that supplement list above. As the Steering Committee reviews this document, we welcome feedback similar to the conversations we had during the meeting on March 11, 2020. If these seem feasible, we can include them in a final summary matrix. Recommendations are provided based on general hazards, followed by hazard specific risk reduction strategies. Where available, these recommendations include example projects from other organizations or cities that have proven successful.

Hazards and Resilience

1. **Uniformity across plans.** Link the effects of climate change to natural hazards in the comprehensive plan. The City of Gresham can look to the NHMP structure for guidance.
2. **Cross-jurisdictional coordination.** Coordinate with other jurisdictions for natural hazard planning beyond earthquakes.¹
3. **Community resilience.** Look to the ORP for guidance on how to address community resilience, livability, and social cohesion into their plans.

Catastrophic Hazards

After analyzing findings from the ORP, Risk Report, and NHMP and comparing our non-regulatory findings with the regulatory findings in Chapter 3, we identified proposed recommendations for Gresham's non-regulatory framework. Some of these include recommendations from the FEMA report, Mitigation Ideas to connect Gresham's natural hazard policy and program framework with FEMA's Risk MAP program. The following recommendations are identified by category so the City can easily identify areas of focus.

1. **Public Engagement.** Strengthen community outreach programs to enhance resilience in the event of a CSZ earthquake. This includes community residents, youth, and local businesses.
 - a. Residents: Gresham has an [earthquake preparedness program](#) that identifies how residents can prepare themselves in the event of a catastrophic hazard. The City can

broaden this to include outreach in the event of a disaster. [Recovers](#), a non-profit organization, focuses on coordination between City staff, local organizations and residents to centralize emergency communication online. Information can be easily linked to social media. Residents can indicate if they have a need, want to give, or want to volunteer. Local organizations manage these requests and offers through partnerships with other local organizations. The City can list resources, emergency and non-emergency contact information. [Hailey, Idaho](#) incorporated this platform as part of their emergency preparedness plan. They used this recovery software when a wildfire occurred in the area in 2013.

- b. Youth: Cascadia Region Earthquake Workgroup (CREW) has educational materials, including a [comic book story](#), available to download for free, telling the story of a high school student after a CSZ earthquake. It provides useful information in an easily readable, visually intriguing format. The City can provide this resource to local schools for libraries to display.
 - c. Businesses: The [Disaster Resistant Business Toolkit Workgroup](#), a non-profit, provides [workshops, trainings, and webinars](#) to assist businesses in planning for disaster resilience. They focus on small to mid-size businesses and non-profits.
 - d. **Regulation.** (a) Develop regulations for safer construction, especially in the communities at greatest risk of earthquake-related hazards. (b) Require seismic bracing for hospital generators, elevators, and vital equipment. (c) Require flexible piping is used when extending water, sewer, and natural gas lines. (d) Require that masonry chimneys of a certain height above roofline be reinforced with steel bracing.
2. **Capital Investments.** (a) Strengthen and retrofit non-reinforced masonry and non-ductile concrete facilities that are vulnerable to ground shaking. (b) Install shutoff valves on water mains. (c) Install window film to prevent injuries from shattered glass. (d) Anchor rooftop-mounted equipment (e.g. HVAC units, satellite dishes).

Chronic Hazards

Landslides

After analyzing the plans, we compared our non-regulatory findings with the regulatory findings in Chapter 3. The following recommendations cover a mixture of regulatory and non-regulatory options for the City of Gresham. Some of these recommendations come from FEMA's Mitigation Ideas.²

1. **Inventory and update knowledge.** (a) Update fact bases of Gresham's regulatory documents to convey Gresham-specific landslide susceptibility. The Risk Report does not identify Gresham-specific landslide susceptibility. (b) Link landslides to the post-CSZ earthquake in the City of Gresham's Comprehensive Plan. (c) Ensure staff resources are being allocated to hillside development inspections.
2. **Preventative.** (a) Control stormwater in landslide-prone areas. (b) Discourage development in landslide risk areas. (c) Consider bond measures or other funding mechanisms designed to set aside more steep slopes as wildlife habitat.
3. **Outreach.** Bolster outreach efforts to educate public on landslide risk along slopes. [DOGAMI](#) created an online resource pamphlet for homeowners, "[A Homeowner's Guide to Landslides for Oregon and Washington.](#)" The City can include this in their online preparation resources. Additionally, the City can place educational signage at parks on the buttes.

Wildfire

The wildfire section of each non-regulatory plan was brief because Gresham, DOGAMI, and Oregon see wildfire as a low-risk chronic hazard. There are areas in the non-regulatory documents that can be enhanced to increase resilience policy for wildfire hazards.

1. **Evaluation.** (a) Evaluate WUI fire risks and post-fire hazards. After a wildfire, the WUI can have an increased risk of flooding and debris flow. For example, areas with vegetation that has deep, thick roots will help prevent post-wildfire geological hazards. Understanding Gresham’s risk of these post-fire hazards will help the City reduce risk during and after these chronic hazard events. (Still need an example). (b) Evaluate transportation network and create Wildfire Evacuation Routes for areas at risk of wildfire.
2. **Actions**
 - **FEMA recommendation:** Implement a fuels management program. There is a federal fuels management program and specific information through the Bureau of Indian Affairs. Local governments are beginning to implement this into the natural hazard program framework based on FEMA’s Mitigation recommendations.
 - Example: [Hill Campus Wetland Vegetation FMP](#)
 - **FEMA recommendation:** Firewise program. Cities and communities across the U.S. have firewise programs. The [Grants Pass Firewise Program provides a brief overview of their program and includes links to the nationwide program with more detail on how to become a firewise community.](#)

Severe Weather

After analyzing the plans, we compared our non-regulatory findings with the regulatory findings in Chapter 3. The following recommendations cover a mixture of regulatory and non-regulatory options for the City of Gresham. Some of these recommendations come from FEMA’s Mitigation Ideas.³

1. **Partnerships.** Partner with Mt. Hood Community College (MHCC) for [climate change mitigation research](#). MHCC is in the process of implementing about 24 projects over the next five to seven years for clean-water retrofitting. Examples include [permeable paving, rain gardens and naturescapes](#) to cool runoff from the college and filter out pollutants. Connect with [Troy Buita](#), Building and Information Management, Mapping and Sustainability Specialist. Through his role of Sustainability Coordinator, he has played an important role in these projects.
2. **Vulnerability**
 - **FEMA recommendation:** Organize outreach to vulnerable populations about severe storm hazards, emergency preparedness information. We are aware that the City’s Communications department is already building relationships with diverse communities in Gresham and urge them to consider incorporating natural hazard preparedness information in discussions with these communities once the relationship is established.
 - **FEMA recommendation:** Bury existing overhead lines, require burying new lines when extending energy and telecommunication infrastructure.

Conclusion

Most of our recommendations are short term, actionable items that address hazards generally, rather than regulations for reducing specific risks. We narrowed them in this way for several reasons: action items are bureaucratically simpler and less costly for the city to implement, use carrots rather than sticks to guide private action, and are less politically troublesome than regulations that could negatively affect certain stakeholders. For these reasons, many of our recommendations involve inventorying, assessment, outreach, and crafting incentives, rather than more regulations, changes to the development code or comprehensive plan, or other process triggers/enforcement mechanisms.

Gresham can do a lot to advance hazard mitigation efforts just by ensuring that inventories of areas and specific structures at risk of different hazards are up to date. For example, a lot of regulation of development in earthquake and landslide-prone areas is done through the Hillside Physical Constraint Overlay District (HPCD); ensuring that Gresham's maps of landslide-prone areas match the data from DOGAMI is crucial to ensuring the HPCD is doing its job. The same principle applies to any actions or policies addressing wildfire risk in wildland-urban interface areas, or other hazards. If the City sufficiently assesses and inventories where the vulnerabilities are, then it is in a much better place to consider what incentive packages, regulations, or capital improvements are appropriate for addressing those risks.

Our recommendations have flexibility in their implementation for this reason. Several of them could be implemented in different "tiers," depending on what is most appropriate for dealing with the risks involved. For example, once the wildland-urban interface areas are inventoried, and the risk to those areas assessed, the city can consider various process triggers to mitigate that hazard. The city may decide that it is most cost-effective to have a Firewise program and outreach effort to homeowners within the wildland-urban interface, encouraging (but not compelling) residents to do certain things to their home and property to reduce the risk associated with wildfires. On the other hand, if the risk is deemed great enough, the city could consider incentive programs or a wildland-urban interface development code to regulate development in these areas.

The overall takeaway from this project is that the city of Gresham is well prepared to mitigate the hazards associated with earthquakes, landslides, and severe storms. Gresham's comprehensive plan and development code cover most of the model best practices for those hazards, as described by FEMA and the state and county hazard documents. The Capital Improvement Plan also includes a multitude of projects aimed at strengthening infrastructure and reducing the risks associated with those hazards. Wildfires are the only hazard type whose best practices for mitigation appear absent from Gresham's policy documents. Climate change is the unpredictable variable that will increase risk as time goes on. The City of Gresham needs to shape patterns of development such that it is resilient to these increasing risks, and we believe these recommendations cover a number of actionable items that will increase the City's resilience to natural hazards without significant cost.

Appendix A: Community Profile Memo

Community Profile and Hazard Assessment

Introduction/Purpose

This memorandum contains a community profile of the City of Gresham, describing demographic and economic data relevant to hazard mitigation. It follows with a short summation of the key hazards for the City of Gresham and previous planning efforts intended to mitigate those hazards. It concludes with an assessment of Gresham's vulnerability to those hazards and the implications/key considerations for future planning efforts. Demographic, socioeconomic, and housing census data for Gresham is summarized and compared to Multnomah County and Oregon for context. Information on Gresham's hazard profile was gathered from the City of Gresham National Hazard Mitigation Plan (June, 2013).

Demographics⁵⁸

Gresham has more families and children than its geographic neighbors. Every age group under 19 years old is larger (as a share of total population) in Gresham than Multnomah, whereas there are **7% fewer prime working age adults (25-55 years old)**. Senior populations are comparable. **Gresham has more family households than Multnomah** (66% to 55%), and many of those have children of the householder present. There are more married couples with children, but also **50% more single-parent households**. **Gresham has a significant Latino population; nearly 20%** of the city's population is Hispanic or Latino (compared to 11.3% in Multnomah County). **Gresham has fewer English-only speaking households, and more Spanish-speaking households.**

Gresham has a less educated populace than the rest of Multnomah County. There are **twice as many 18 to 24-year-old people who did not graduate high school**, and only 4% have a bachelor's degree (compared to 15% in all of Multnomah). For the population 25 years or older, **23% have a bachelor's degree or higher**, compared to 45% in the rest of the county. **5% fewer individuals have a broadband connection at home** in Gresham compared to the rest of the county.

Income and Poverty⁵⁹

Gresham's median household income is approximately \$10k less per year than Multnomah County, and \$15k less for families. Distribution of incomes is comparable to the county and state in the categories below \$100k/year (the rest of Multnomah County has a significant number of families whose annual income exceeds \$150k). **Gresham has a greater degree of child/family poverty** than its geographic neighbors. The overall population in poverty is 4% greater than Multnomah County, but there are **8% more minors (people under 18) and 13% more children under the age of five living in poverty** compared to the rest of the county. The difference between Gresham and the state of Oregon is similar. When poverty is broken down by race and ethnicity, Gresham has **more Native Hawaiian, Hispanic, some other race alone, and white individuals in poverty** (+12%, 8%, 6%, and 4% respectively).

⁵⁸ See end of Appendix A for tables. All data from American Community Survey 2017 (5 year).

⁵⁹ See end of Appendix A for tables. All data from American Community Survey 2017 (5 year).

Housing⁶⁰

53% of Gresham's housing are 1-unit, detached structures; the second most common are structures with 20 or more units (12%). One-third of Gresham's housing stock has 3 or more units. Gresham has fewer high density (20+ units) structures than Multnomah County, but more with 3-19 units. **The vast majority of Gresham's housing was built in the latter half of the 20th century. 56% was built between 1960 and 1989.** Another 18% was built between 1990 and 1999, and 13% between 2000 and 2009. Monthly owner/renter costs as percentage of household income: **67% of Gresham's renters are cost-burdened** (rent >30% of income), compared to 54% for the rest of the county. Owner cost/income ratios are comparable to Multnomah County: 34% of owners with a mortgage and 15% without a mortgage are cost-burdened.

60% of Gresham's homes are worth \$150k to \$300k. There are 24% more homes in this price range than the rest of Multnomah County. 24% of Gresham homes are worth \$300k-500k. **The dominant heating source is electricity, upon which 51% of households rely.** This is 9% more than the rest of the county, which has a greater share of dependence on fossil fuels (utility gas, fuel oil, kerosene, etc.).

Risk/Hazard Profile

The June 2013 City of Gresham Natural Hazards Mitigation Plan assesses the city's exposure to a dozen different hazards (natural and artificial). The analysis is "relative;" it does not predict the individual likelihood of a hazard occurrence, but the relative likelihood of each hazard compared to others in the analysis. For natural hazards, **earthquake** and **severe weather/storms** had the greatest relative likelihood. Gresham is at moderate risk of **volcano/ash fallout**. Finally, **flooding, landslide, and WUI (wildland-urban interface) fire** were scored as the natural hazards with the lowest relative likelihood ([p.3-4 Gresham NHMP](#)).⁶¹

Earthquake

The entirety of the city is vulnerable to earthquakes due to faults in the Cascadia Subduction Zone, upon which Gresham is built. By nature, earthquakes generally affect large swaths of area rather than individual jurisdictions. Homes, critical facilities, and infrastructure built near fault lines are at risk of damage from fault slip (measured in "moment magnitude") and soil liquefaction. Liquefaction is when a solid soil medium attains liquid qualities, due to disturbance or excessive moisture content. For this reason, areas with soft soils near rivers/bodies of water are the most susceptible to liquefaction. Infrastructure built on liquefiable soils is most susceptible to severe damage. Earthquakes can lead to secondary hazards, such as landslides along steep slopes, and fires or flooding from damaged infrastructure.

Severe weather/storms

Severe weather – including high winds, snow, and ice storms – can affect the entire region. The Cascade Mountain Range creates a low-pressure zone above Multnomah County which, when combined with precipitation and uninterrupted high winds from the south or the Columbia River gorge, create conditions for severe winter storms.⁶² Heavy rainfall can wash away low-drainage soils and overload stormwater

⁶⁰ See end of Appendix A for tables. All data from American Community Survey 2017 (5 year).

⁶¹ Gresham 2013 Natural Hazards Mitigation Plan, 3-4 (p.30)

⁶² Multnomah County 2017 Natural Hazards Mitigation Plan, 3-8 (p.144)

systems, potentially leading to secondary hazards (like flooding and landslides). Windstorms can damage aboveground infrastructure, creating power outages and interrupting communications. Snow and ice inhibit and incapacitate transportation networks, making travel difficult for citizens and emergency responders alike.

Volcano/ash fallout

Volcanic eruptions are not common, but due to Gresham's proximity to the Cascade Mountain Range, it is vulnerable to an event similar to the eruption of Mount Saint Helens in 1980.⁶³ These events cause a multitude of individual risks stemming from blast effects, lava (molten rock) and pyroclastic (hot ash/rock fragments) flows, and lahars or mudflows (when snow/ice-laden soil rapidly melts and liquefies). There is a secondary risk of fires caused by volcanic eruption. All of Gresham is vulnerable to the effects of a volcanic eruption.

Flood

Risk of flood is most prevalent in floodplains, low-lying areas near rivers that routinely flood. Parts of Gresham are adjacent to or contain floodplains for the Columbia and Sandy Rivers, as well as Johnson Creek and Fairview Creek. Major flooding events can inundate homes and streets with water, destroy critical infrastructure, and inhibit emergency response and evacuation. Secondary hazards arise from the dispersal of fuel and other contaminants, as well as interruption of electricity and communications. 400,000 square feet of building space is located within Gresham's floodplains, most of which is Low Density Residential and Light Industrial. The unincorporated communities of Pleasant Valley and Springwater are at elevated risk of flooding, due to the proximity and frequent flooding of the Johnson Creek and Fairview Creek.

Landslide

Landslides are common where there are soft-soils and steep slopes, and often catalyzed by other natural hazards (flooding, severe storms, earthquakes). Seismic shock or liquefaction will cause earth and debris to flow, damaging buildings and infrastructure on its way down. Gresham's hilly areas and buttes are particularly prone to landslides, especially those where the slope gradient is in excess of 35%. Southern Gresham and the unincorporated communities of Pleasant Valley and Springwater are at the most risk of landslides, due to their proximity to heavily sloped land and buttes.

Wildland-Urban-Interface Fire

Wildfires threaten communities in the wildland/urban interface, areas where development ends and is abutted by open-space with the potential for ignition. Fires that start in the wilderness can ignite structures that are close to the wildland/urban interface, which then has the potential of igniting other nearby structures, starting a destructive chain of events. For this reason, any development near to this wildland/urban interface is at risk of WUI fires. The risk is elevated when there is no defensible space, limitations to access for emergency personnel, lack of water, presence of fuels and other potential ignition sources, and lack of communication/outreach about fire safety. Southern Gresham and the

⁶³ Gresham 2013 Natural Hazards Mitigation Plan, 3-16 (p.42)

unincorporated communities of Pleasant Valley and Springwater are at the most risk of WUI fires, due to their proximity to forested areas and open space.⁶⁴

Implications/Conclusions

- Disaster burdens disproportionately fall upon individuals in vulnerable populations. Children and the elderly are the most vulnerable in times of crises, and Gresham has more children and family households than its neighbors.⁶⁵ Greater numbers of single parent households and children in poverty suggest a vulnerability for the city of Gresham. Planning for community centers and outreach to provide family-centric emergency resources is crucial.
- Minority/immigrant communities are more vulnerable to hazards, due to past real estate discrimination, language barriers to emergency communication, and lack of community resources/personal assets. This could be elevated by lack of internet connectivity. Gresham's significant Latino/Spanish-speaking population should be considered in their emergency planning and multilingual outreach efforts.
- Those who have lower incomes or are in poverty are also disproportionately affected by disasters. Individuals and families without financial assets are less able to prepare for emergencies and recover from the costs of disastrous events. Lower education positively correlates with various socioeconomic indicators of poverty: lower income, housing cost burden, etc. Gresham's population has more families and children in poverty; these populations will need additional support during times of crises. This is especially true for impoverished single-parent households with children, who're usually associated with lower socioeconomic status, and carry more personal child care burden than married households. This intersection of poor households with children and a larger number of single-parent households presents a potential vulnerability for the City of Gresham.
- Poor households are more likely to be renters than owners. Special attention should be paid to the enforcement of disaster-proof construction/retrofit for rental properties, particularly those with a higher number of units per structure (which are more likely to be available/affordable to those with limited incomes). Since renters are more likely to be cost-burdened, they will need more assistance/resources in an emergency, and the loss of property will generally have a greater impact on these individuals and their assets than those in single-family homes.
- Greater reliance on electricity for heating makes those households more vulnerable to interruptions in/damage to the electric grid.
- All of Gresham and its people are vulnerable to the effects of earthquakes, severe storms, and volcanic eruptions. Elevated risks of flooding, landslide, and wildfire exist where there are localized conditions for these events. Areas in Gresham with elevated risk of those events include the Columbia and Sandy floodplains, Southern Gresham, Pleasant/Happy Valley, and Springwater.

⁶⁴ Gresham 2013 Natural Hazards Mitigation Plan, 3-20 (p.46)

⁶⁵ Multnomah County 2017 Natural Hazards Mitigation Plan, 2-8 (p.18)

Age distribution		Oregon	Multnomah County	Gresham	Diff
Under 5 years	5.8%	5.8%	6.7%	0.9%	
5 to 9 years	6.0%	5.7%	7.3%	1.6%	
10 to 14 years	6.0%	5.0%	7.0%	2.0%	
15 to 19 years	6.1%	5.1%	6.7%	1.6%	
20 to 24 years	6.6%	6.3%	6.8%	0.5%	
25 to 34 years	13.9%	18.6%	14.5%	-4.1%	
35 to 44 years	13.1%	16.1%	13.4%	-2.7%	
45 to 54 years	12.8%	13.0%	12.6%	-0.4%	
55 to 59 years	6.7%	6.0%	6.6%	0.6%	
60 to 64 years	6.8%	6.0%	5.8%	-0.2%	
65 to 74 years	9.8%	7.5%	7.4%	-0.1%	
75 to 84 years	4.5%	3.1%	3.5%	0.4%	
85 years+	2.1%	1.6%	1.8%	0.2%	
Under 19	23.9%	21.6%	27.7%	6.1%	
20-44	33.6%	41.0%	34.7%	-6.3%	
45-64	26.3%	25.0%	25.0%	0.0%	
65+	16.4%	12.2%	12.7%	0.5%	
Prime working age (25-55)	39.8%	47.7%	40.5%	-7.2%	

Ethnicity/Race		Oregon	Multnomah County	Gresham	Diff
White	89.1%	82.7%	82.6%	-0.1%	
Black or African American	2.8%	7.2%	7.4%	0.2%	
American Indian and Alaska Native	3.1%	2.5%	3.2%	0.7%	
Asian	5.6%	9.2%	6.2%	-3.0%	
Hawaiian & other Pacific Islander	0.8%	1.1%	1.5%	0.4%	
Some other race	3.5%	3.4%	5.8%	2.4%	
Hispanic or Latino (of any race)	12.7%	11.3%	19.6%	8.3%	
Born in United States	88.9%	84.4%	82.0%	-2.4%	
Born in Puerto Rico, U.S. Island areas, or born abroad to American	1.2%	1.4%	1.2%	-0.2%	
Foreign born	9.9%	14.2%	16.9%	2.7%	
Language Spoken at Home					
English only	84.8%	80.0%	73.7%	-6.3%	
Language other than English	15.2%	20.0%	26.3%	6.3%	
Spanish	9.0%	8.2%	15.5%	7.3%	
Other Indo-European languages	2.6%	4.7%	5.8%	1.1%	
Asian and Pacific Islander languages	3.0%	5.7%	3.6%	-2.1%	
Other languages	0.6%	1.5%	1.5%	0.0%	
Computer/Internet Connection					
Total households	1,571,631	318,173	39,281		
With a computer	90.5%	91.8%	88.9%	-2.9%	
With a broadband Internet subscript	81.9%	84.1%	79.3%	-4.8%	

Family Composition	Oregon		Multnomah County	
				Gresham
Total households	1,571,631		318,173	39,281
Family households (families)	63%		55%	66%
With own children of the householder under 18 years	26%		25%	32%
Married-couple family	49%		40%	45%
With own children of the householder under 18 years	18%		17%	21%
Male householder, no wife present, family	4%		4%	6%
With own children of the householder under 18 years	2%		2%	3%
Female householder, no husband present, family	10%		10%	15%
With own children of the householder under 18 years	6%		6%	9%
Nonfamily households	37%		45%	34%
Householder living alone	28%		32%	26%
65 years and over	11%		10%	11%
Households with one or more people under 18 years	29%		27%	36%
Households with one or more people 65 years and over	30%		22%	26%
Education				
	Multnomah County		Gresham	Difference
Population 18 to 24 years				
Less than high school graduate	11%		24%	13%
High school graduate (includes equivalency)	33%		36%	3%
Some college or associate's degree	41%		37%	-4%
Bachelor's degree or higher	15%		4%	-12%
Population 25 years and over				
Less than 9th grade	4%		5%	2%
9th to 12th grade, no diploma	4%		6%	1%
High school graduate (includes equivalency)	18%		28%	10%
Some college, no degree	21%		29%	8%
Associate's degree	8%		10%	2%
Bachelor's degree	27%		15%	-13%
Graduate or professional degree	18%		8%	-10%
Percent high school graduate or higher	92%		89%	-3%
Percent bachelor's degree or higher	45%		23%	-23%

Incomes	Oregon		Multnomah		Gresham		Difference between Gresham & Multnomah	
	Households	Families	Households	Families	Households	Families	Households	Families
Total	1,571,631	994,742	318,173	174,076	39,281	25,865		
Less than \$10,000	7%	4%	8%	5%	6%	6%	-1%	2%
\$10,000 to \$14,999	5%	3%	5%	2%	6%	3%	1%	1%
\$15,000 to \$24,999	10%	7%	9%	6%	12%	9%	3%	2%
\$25,000 to \$34,999	10%	9%	9%	7%	11%	8%	2%	1%
\$35,000 to \$49,999	14%	13%	12%	12%	14%	13%	2%	2%
\$50,000 to \$74,999	19%	20%	17%	17%	20%	21%	2%	4%
\$75,000 to \$99,999	13%	15%	13%	14%	12%	15%	-1%	0%
\$100,000 to \$149,999	14%	17%	15%	19%	14%	18%	-1%	-1%
\$150,000 to \$199,999	5%	7%	6%	8%	3%	4%	-2%	-3%
\$200,000 or more	5%	7%	7%	10%	2%	3%	-5%	-7%
Median income (dollars)	56,119	69,031	60,369	76,557	50,675	60,999	-9694	-15558
Mean income (dollars)	75,851	89,078	83,642	101,108	63,636	72,491	-20006	-28617

Poverty	Multnomah		Gresham	Difference between Gresham & Multnomah
	Oregon	County		
Population for whom poverty status is determined	15%	16%	20%	4%
Under 18 years	19%	21%	29%	8%
Under 5 years	22%	20%	33%	13%
5 to 17 years	18%	21%	28%	7%
Related children of householder under 18	19%	20%	29%	9%
18 to 64 years	15%	16%	19%	3%
18 to 34 years	21%	21%	24%	3%
35 to 64 years	12%	13%	16%	3%
60 years and over	9%	12%	9%	-3%
				0%
White alone	14%	14%	18%	4%
Black or African American alone	31%	36%	34%	-2%
American Indian and Alaska Native alone	26%	31%	31%	0%
Asian alone	16%	18%	9%	-9%
Hawaiian & other Pacific Islander alone	26%	23%	35%	12%
Some other race alone	22%	27%	33%	6%
Two or more races	20%	21%	21%	0%
Hispanic or Latino origin (of any race)	24%	29%	37%	8%
				0%
Civilian labor force 16 years and over	10%	11%	13%	2%
Employed	8%	9%	10%	2%
Unemployed	35%	43%	39%	-4%

Structural Characteristics	Multnomah		Gresham	Difference between Gresham & Multnomah
	County			
UNITS IN STRUCTURE				
Total housing units	337,821	41,611		
1-unit, detached	56%	53%		-3%
1-unit, attached	5%	8%		3%
2 units	4%	3%		-1%
3 or 4 units	6%	7%		1%
5 to 9 units	5%	7%		2%
10 to 19 units	6%	7%		1%
20 or more units	17%	12%		-5%
Mobile home	2%	3%		1%
Boat, RV, van, etc.	0%	0%		0%
YEAR STRUCTURE BUILT				
Built 2014 or later	1%	1%		0%
Built 2010 to 2013	2%	1%		-1%
Built 2000 to 2009	11%	13%		2%
Built 1990 to 1999	11%	18%		8%
Built 1980 to 1989	8%	17%		9%
Built 1970 to 1979	14%	27%		14%
Built 1960 to 1969	9%	12%		2%
Built 1950 to 1959	11%	6%		-5%
Built 1940 to 1949	8%	2%		-5%
Built 1939 or earlier	26%	3%		-23%
HOUSE HEATING FUEL				
Utility gas	50%	45%		-5%
Bottled, tank, or LP gas	1%	1%		-1%
Electricity	42%	51%		9%
Fuel oil, kerosene, etc.	4%	1%		-3%
Coal or coke	0%	0%		0%
Wood	2%	2%		0%
Solar energy	0%	0%		0%
Other fuel	1%	0%		0%
No fuel used	1%	0%		0%

Home Value			
	Multnomah		
VALUE	County	Gresham	Difference between Gresham & Multnomah
Owner-occupied units	172,892	20,881	
Less than \$50,000	4%	7%	3%
\$50,000 to \$99,999	1%	2%	1%
\$100,000 to \$149,999	4%	5%	2%
\$150,000 to \$199,999	9%	18%	8%
\$200,000 to \$299,999	26%	42%	16%
\$300,000 to \$499,999	35%	24%	-11%
\$500,000 to \$999,999	19%	3%	-17%
\$1,000,000 or more	3%	0%	-2%
Cost/Income Ratios			
SELECTED MONTHLY OWNER COSTS AS A PERCENTAGE OF HOUSEHOLD INCOME			
Housing units with a mortgage	126,699	15,157	
Less than 20.0 percent	38%	34%	-5%
20.0 to 24.9 percent	17%	17%	0%
25.0 to 29.9 percent	12%	15%	3%
30.0 to 34.9 percent	8%	7%	-2%
35.0 percent or more	25%	27%	2%
Housing unit without a mortgage	44,995	5,607	
Less than 10.0 percent	37%	37%	0%
10.0 to 14.9 percent	21%	23%	2%
15.0 to 19.9 percent	11%	11%	0%
20.0 to 24.9 percent	8%	9%	1%
25.0 to 29.9 percent	5%	5%	1%
30.0 to 34.9 percent	4%	2%	-2%
35.0 percent or more	15%	13%	-2%
GROSS RENT AS A PERCENTAGE OF HOUSEHOLD INCOME			
Occupied units paying rent (exclu	138,993	16,476	
Less than 15.0 percent	11%	5%	-6%
15.0 to 19.9 percent	11%	3%	-8%
20.0 to 24.9 percent	13%	15%	3%
25.0 to 29.9 percent	11%	10%	-1%
30.0 to 34.9 percent	10%	14%	4%
35.0 percent or more	44%	53%	9%
Cost-burdened	54%	67%	13%

Appendix B: Methods of Analysis

Figure 10. Content Analysis Approach

Interview Guide

Each member of the IPRE Team conducted an interview with a member of the Steering Committee advising the Natural Hazards Policy and Program project. The following questions were asked of each Committee member.

- I. **General Information.** First, we'd like to learn a bit more about you.
 - a. Can you describe your role at the City of Gresham?
- II. **Information about hazard policies.** Now we'd like to learn more about natural hazard and community resilience policies in Gresham.
 - a. What does hazard mitigation mean to you in your role or within your department at the City? How about resilience?
 - b. In what ways does your work deal with mitigating natural hazards and improving resilience through policies and code?
- III. **Information about hazard regulatory framework and code.** Part of our project is to evaluate how well hazard mitigation is being implemented in city codes and ordinances. These final questions relate to the City's regulatory framework.
 - a. In your opinion, how well is hazard mitigation being implemented in city codes and ordinances? (note: differentiate between regulatory and non-regulatory)
 - b. In your role or within your department, can you describe obstacles experienced in implementing hazard mitigation?
 - c. If so, what tools or policy changes are needed to overcome such obstacles to implementing hazard mitigation? (note: differentiate between regulatory and non-regulatory)
- IV. **Conclusion.** To conclude our interview, we have some follow up questions.
 - a. Can you direct us to anyone outside of the steering committee who would be beneficial to speak to on these topics?
 - b. Is there anything we missed or anything you would like to add?